

MYCOLOGY-IV PROCEEDINGS

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Publishing: Gerelt Nikko

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Associate Professor WANG HAIYAN
Vegetable and Flower Research Institute
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Animal Husbandry Sciences
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Academic Background

Wang Haiyan graduated from Jilin Agricultural University.

Research interests

- ✓ Collection and evaluation of edible mushroom germplasm resources
- ✓ Breeding of new edible mushroom varieties
- ✓ Edible mushroom cultivation technology

Intellectual property

- ✓ Major contributor to the Second Prize of Science and Technology Progress Award of Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region
- ✓ Led more than 10 scientific research projects
- ✓ Bred 6 new edible mushroom varieties
- ✓ Obtained 2 international invention patents and 5 national invention patents
- ✓ Led the formulation of 7 local standards
- ✓ Received 3 agricultural extension technologies recognized by the Autonomous Region
- ✓ Participated in the compilation of 4 monographs
- ✓ Published over 30 related academic papers

Doctor (Ph.D) Ryota KATAOKA

Department of Local Produce and Food Sciences, Faculty of Life and Environmental Sciences, University of Yamanashi

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Academic Background

Kyoto University, Ph.D (Agriculture) 2005 - 2008

Tokyo University of Agriculture, M.Sc. (Agricultural chemistry) 2002 – 2004

Field of Interests

- ✓ Soil Science, Soil Microbial Ecology
- ✓ Soil biochemistry, Soil quality
- ✓ Agriculture and Environment
- ✓ Effective use of unused resources
- ✓ Mushroom production using foodwastes

Research Assistant ZHIYING DING

Department of Biology
Inner Mongolia Academy of Agricultural & Animal Husbandry Sciences

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Academic Background

Earn a master's degree from Inner Mongolia University.

Research interests

- ✓ Edible mushroom germplasm resources**
- ✓ Edible Mushroom Cultivation
- ✓ Bioactive compounds from edible fungi

Intellectual property

- ✓ Optimization of Liquid Spawn Culture Medium Formulation for *Pleurotus citrinopileatus*

Doctor (Ph.D) ERDENE Zundui

Department of Biotechnology and Breeding
School of Biotechnology and Animal Science,
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Academic Background

Erdene received her Ph.D from the Mongolian University of Life Sciences in Mongolia.

Research interests

- ✓ Edible and medicinal mushroom cultivation technology
- ✓ Mushroom biotechnology
- ✓ Beneficial microorganism research
- ✓ Animal feed additives

Intellectual property

- ✓ Worked on 15 scientific research projects
- ✓ Published over 10 related academic papers

Doctor (Ph.D), Professor SACHIN GUPTA

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Agriculture
Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural
Sciences and Technology-Jammu
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Academic Background

Dr. Sachin Gupta received his Ph.D from the Sher-e-Kashmir University of Agricultural Sciences and Technology-Jammu

Research interests

- ✓ Substrate and Cultivation Technology standardization of Edible and Medicinal Mushrooms
- ✓ Biochemical extraction from medicinal mushrooms
- ✓ Value addition of mushrooms

Doctor (Ph.D) BURENBAATAR Ganbaatar
Sector of Fungi and Lichen Genetical Resources
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Academic Background

Burenbaatar Ganbaatar completed his Bachelor's degree in Ecology at the Mongolian University of Life Sciences from 2000 to 2004. He later earned a Master's degree in Plant Science with specialization in Mycology from the National University of Mongolia between 2009 and 2013. From 2019 to 2025, he pursued doctoral studies in Mycology at Jilin Agricultural University, China, where he successfully obtained a PhD focusing on macrofungal diversity, taxonomy, and molecular systematics. His academic training combines traditional fungal taxonomy with modern molecular biological approaches, with a particular emphasis on the diversity and conservation of macrofungi in Mongolia.

Research Interests

- ✓ Taxonomy and systematics of macrofungi, with a special focus on *Lycoperdaceae*, *Geastraceae*, and related groups
- ✓ Macrofungal diversity, distribution, and conservation in Mongolia and Central Asia
- ✓ Integration of classical taxonomy and molecular phylogenetics in fungal research
- ✓ Ecology and biogeography of edible, medicinal, and rare fungal species
- ✓ Documentation, databasing, and herbarium management of fungal collections
- ✓ Conservation assessment and Red List evaluation of fungi
- ✓ Applied mycology, including food safety, medicinal potential, and sustainable use of mushrooms

**Doctor (Ph.D) WOOD TIMIPANIPIRI
THANKGOD**

Centre Director, Bioresource Development
Centre

Odi National Biotechnology Research and
Development Agency, Nigeria. Department of
Biology, Bayelsa Medical University, Bayelsa
State, Nigeria.

Academic Background

Academically, he studied Plant science and Biotechnology at the University of Port Harcourt (2000-2004), Post Graduate in Education, University of Port Harcourt. Postgraduate Diploma in Microbiology, FUTO, Owerri; MSc in Plant Genetics and Molecular Biology, University of Ibadan; PhD in Fungi Biotechnology, University of Ibadan, all in Nigeria.

He has held several positions in NBRDA such as; Head of Plant Tissue Culture (2010-2011); Head, Mushroom Production and Research Unit (2011- 2014); Head, Plant Bioresource Division (2014-2018); and Head, Animal Bioresources Division (2018-2019). In 2022, he was appointed as Strategic Board Member for a functional Mushroom company, Doseology Sciences, in British Columbia, Canada to provide technical advice (online) for growing and processing Magic mushroom (*Psilocybe cubensis*). He later became a Technical Director for an Afro-American mushroom company in Ibadan (2022 – 2025).

In 2025, he was appointed as the Centre Coordinator, BIODC Odi. He has dozens of research publications to his name. In addition, he is the National Assistant Secretary, National Mushroom Growers, Processor, and Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (NAMGPMAN).

Research interests

- ✓ Edible and medicinal mushroom cultivation technology
- ✓ Mushroom biotechnology
- ✓ Plant Tissue Culture
- ✓ Molecular Biology
- ✓ Bioresources

Doctor (Ph.D) KHERLENCHIMEG Nyamsuren
Sector of Fungi and Lichen Genetical Resources
Botanic Garden and Research Institute,
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Academic Background

Since 1998, She has been conducting research at the Institute focused on the taxonomy of fungi, assessment of fungal resources, and evaluation of their conservation status. Her work includes enriching the Mongolian fungal collection (Herbarium FUBA). She has contributed to several significant publications and projects. She published books Atlas of Distribution and Resources of Forest Associated Resources (2011); Red Book of Mongolia(2013); Illustrated Guide to Mongolian Fungi (2016); Conspectus of Mongolian Higher Fungi (2017); Red List of Mongolia's Flora, Volume II (2019); Biodiversity of Mongolia: Checklist of Plants, Fungi, and Microorganisms, Volume II (2019); Red List of Non-Vascular Plants of Mongolia, Volume III (2020); Volume 3a of the series "Fungal Flora of Mongolia" (2022); 46 scientific articles (17 international) and presented 42 seminar papers (5 international). Authored 4 manuals/guidelines and 8 standards.

Research Interests

- ✓ Taxonomy and systematics of macrofungi, with a special focus on Russulales,Boletales, Agaricales and related groups
- ✓ Macrofungal diversity, distribution, and conservation in Mongolia
- ✓ Integration of classical taxonomy and molecular phylogenetics in fungal research
- ✓ Ecology and biogeography of edible, medicinal, and rare fungal species
- ✓ Documentation, databasing, and herbarium management of fungal collections
- ✓ Conservation assessment and redlist (IUCN) evaluation of fungi

Master (Ms.C) LI YAJIAO

Biophysics

Inner Mongolia Academy of Agricultural &
Animal Husbandry Sciencese-mail: 726450605@qq.com**Academic Background**

Li Yajiao received her Master's degree from Inner Mongolia University.

Research interests

- ✓ Innovation in Edible Mushroom Germplasm Resources and Breeding of New Varieties
- ✓ Research and Development of High-Efficiency Cultivation Technology for Edible Mushrooms

Intellectual property

- ✓ Li Yajiao, Sun Guoqin, Guo Jiufeng, Wang Haiyan, & Pang Jie. (2020). Molecular evolution and phylogenetics of main wild mushrooms from Xilingol Grassland in Inner Mongolia. *Jiangsu Agricultural Sciences*, 48(09), 86-92.
- ✓ Li Yajiao, Sun Guoqin, Yu Chuanzong, Wang Haiyan, Pang Jie, & Guo Jiufeng. (2022). Preliminary study on a new species of Agaricaceae from Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region. *Edible Fungi of China*, 41(3), 12-16+24.

Master (Ms.C) RIAZ AHMED

Department of Agriculture Government of Sindh

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Academic Background

A highly accomplished Agricultural Engineer and Extension Services & Management professional with over 32 years of progressive experience, including five years in senior project management, within the Agriculture Department, Government of Sindh. Demonstrated success in delivering sustainable outcomes while serving in key technical and leadership roles at the district, divisional, and provincial levels, including Deputy Secretary (Technical), Director Agriculture Extension, Executive District Officer, and Project Director.

Possesses strong expertise in sustainable agriculture, natural resource and water management, risk management, crop protection, and efficient farming systems. Has contributed to the implementation of a World Bank–funded Nutrition Sensitive Agriculture project and has proven capability in developing PC-I proposals aligned with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

A recognized leader in promoting integrated and alternative approaches to reduce pesticide use, with a strong record of managing multidisciplinary teams and delivering projects within defined timelines and budgets. Holds Master's degrees in Agricultural Engineering and Economics, combining technical depth with economic and policy insight.

Experienced in preparing high-level reports, summaries, and policy briefs, and representing institutions at national and international forums, supported by participation in multiple global training programs and conferences.

Doctor (Ph.D) MUNKHGEREL Lodonjav
Laboratory of Phytochemistry and Technology
Institute of Chemistry and Chemical
Technology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences
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Academic Background

Munkhgerel Lodonjav completed her Bachelor's degree in Chemistry at the National University of Mongolia in 1997. She later earned a Master's degree in chemical technologist from Ulaanbaatar University, Mongolia, in 2003. In 2015, she successfully obtained a doctor (PhD) in Chemistry in Mongolia, focusing on interferon-like activity and phytochemical investigations of *Agaricus silvaticus* Schaeff.

Research Interests

- ✓ Isolation, structural characterization, and bioactivity evaluation of secondary metabolites from plants and mushrooms.
- ✓ Studies on lipids and fatty acids from animal, plant, and fungal sources.
- ✓ Development of mushroom-derived products through chemical, biological, and pharmacological research.
- ✓ Technological development of carbohydrate-based materials for food, medical, and light industries.
- ✓ Design and synthesis of nanoparticles for biomedical applications.

Doctor (Ph.D) SOLONGO Khadbaatar

Department of Plant Taxonomy
Botanic Garden and Research Institute,
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Academic Background

Solongo Khadbaatar completed her Bachelor's degree in Biology with a specialisation in Botany at the National University of Mongolia from 2001 to 2005. She later earned a Master's degree in Botany from the same university between 2010 and 2014, with a focus on morphometric analysis within the genus *Ranunculus* (Plant taxonomy). From 2019 to 2025, she pursued doctoral studies in Botany at Jilin Agricultural University, China, where she successfully obtained a PhD focusing on the resource investigation of rare medicinal mushrooms, chemotaxonomy, metabolomics, and the pharmacological mechanisms of *Inonotus hispidus*. Her academic training integrates classical plant taxonomy and chemotaxonomy with modern biochemical and metabolomic approaches, and places a strong emphasis on the study, conservation, and sustainable use of plant and fungal resources in Mongolia.

Research Interests

- ✓ Plant taxonomy and systematics
- ✓ Flora of Mongolia and plant diversity documentation
- ✓ Chemotaxonomy of rare Medicinal Mushrooms
- ✓ Plant conservation, including Red List assessments
- ✓ Ecosystem and biodiversity monitoring
- ✓ Vegetation dynamics and habitat restoration (peatlands)

Doctor (Ph.D) ZULJARGAL Gantumur
Vegetable and Flower Research Institute
Livestock Technology Advancement Center
Mongolian University of Life Sciences
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Academic Background

Zuljargal Gantumur graduated from Hankyong National University.

Research interests

- ✓ Meat processing technology
- ✓ Functional food

Published papers

- ✓ Zuljargal, G., Chimegee, N., & Dashmaa, D. (2023). Fatty acid profile and lipid oxidation of dry aged beef. *Mongolian Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 16(38), 1-6.
- ✓ Zuljargal, G., Shin, J. Y., & Kim, H. S. (2026). Antioxidant Activity and Quality Evaluation of Ham Enriched with Mushroom Powders. *Food and Life*.
- ✓ Zuljargal, G., Koh, M. J., & Kim, H. S. (2026). Enrichment of meat products with oyster mushroom: A Review. *Food and Life*.

Oral presentation

- ✓ Antioxidant Activity and Quality Evaluation of Meat Products Enhanced with Mushroom Powders, /57th KOSFA International Symposium and Annual Meeting/
- ✓ Enhancement of Antioxidant Activity and Quality Characteristics of Pork Patties Enriched with Oyster Mushroom Powder, /Korean Society of Dairy and Food Science/

Doctor (Ph.D) TSETSEG Baljinova

Honourable member

Laboratory of Microbiology, Institute of Biology,
Mongolian Academy of Sciences (MAS)e-mail: tsetseg110@gmail.com;
tsetseg_b@mas.ac.mn**Academic Background**

Tsetseg Baljinova completed her Bachelor's and Master's degrees in Biochemistry with specialization in Microbiology at Lomonosov Moscow State University from 1966 to 1971. Her Master's degree research concentrated on fibrinolytic proteases produced by actinomycetes of the genus *Nocardia*, dynamics of their formation, isolation, purification and gel-filtration chromatography. In 1977-1981 she pursued doctoral (candidate of sciences) studies in the above University focusing on studies of the effects of antibiotics on growth and activities of enzymes of the carbon metabolism of actinomycetes of the genera *Streptomyces* and *Nocardia*. Subsequently, she has been trained in bacterial genetics (Romania), in isolation and identification of bioactive compounds produced by actinomycetes (Bulgaria, Germany and Russia) and in methods of traditional and modern taxonomy of actinomycetes (Bulgaria, Japan, Russia and the UK). She also was trained in molecular identification of microfungi in Japan. She had a short-time trainings in agricultural (the Philippines) and environmental biotechnologies (Thailand).

After graduation from the University, she started her research career at the Institute of Biology, MAS, Ulaanbaatar, focusing on investigation of microorganisms inhabiting the rhizosphere of the steppe, desert-steppe and desert plants of Mongolia with emphasis on actinomycetes. In 1976 together with academician Puntsag T. she published the first in Mongolia paper on diversity of microscopic fungi found in the rhizosphere of the desert, desert-steppe and steppe plants. At present her research portfolio contains 75 genera of actinomycetes,

including one new genus and nine new species, and their biological activities. Her portfolio as a project leader comprises also the data on diversity of Mongolian prokaryotic microorganisms embracing 152 genera of 61 Families, 28 Orders and 8 Classes of the Domains *Bacteria* and *Archaea* and eukaryotic microorganisms consisting of 178 genera of fungi, 22 genera of yeasts and 6 genera of *Chromista*. Dr. Tsetseg B. is a member of the TWAS and the country representative in the Asian Mycological Association (AMA).

Research Interests

- ✓ Ecology, diversity and taxonomy of prokaryotic and eukaryotic microorganisms
- ✓ Microbial bio-active compounds

Master (M.Sc) BINDERIYA Amgalan-Enkh

Genbank of Natural Plants

Botanic Garden and Research Institute,

Mongolian Academy of Sciences

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Academic Background

Received a Master of Biotechnology degree in “Phylogenetic Applications of DNA from Herbarium Specimens: The Case of genus for *Astragalus* L. and *Oxytropis* DC” from the National University of Mongolia. Since 2025, she has worked as a researcher in the Genebank of the Natural Plant at the Botanic Garden and Research Institute.

Research interests

- ✓ Molecular biology
- ✓ Gene engineering
- ✓ Plant biotechnology
- ✓ Molecular diagnostics

Doctor (Ph.D) GOOMARAL Altansukh
Department of Biotechnology and Breeding
School of Animal Science and Biotechnology,
Mongolian University of Life Sciences.
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Academic Background

Tottori University, Japan

- ✓ Degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Bioenvironmental Science in the United Graduate School of Agriculture Sciences, 2013
- ✓ Moscow Agricultural Academy named after K.A. Timiryazev, Russia. Faculty of Agriculture
- ✓ Master of Science in Plant Genetics and Breeding, 2003

Field of Interests

- ✓ Characterization and evaluation of mycorrhizal fungi
- ✓ Characterization, evaluation, conservation, and effective utilization of plant genetic resources by using advanced techniques of biotechnology
- ✓ Ecological study of a semi-desert pastoral area in the country

Doctor (Ph.D) Enkhtuya Ochirbat
Sector of Fungi and Lichen Genetic Resources
Botanic Garden and Research Institute,
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Academic background

She works at the Institute of Botanical Garden of the Mongolian Academy of Sciences, from a research fellow to a leading researcher in the fields of taxonomy, origin, role in ecosystems, ecology, conservation, and significance of Mongolian lichens. In 2000, she received her doctorate in biological sciences. Thanks to her, the gene pool of Mongolian lichens has been expanded by approximately 3,000 collections, 1,079 species have been assigned Mongolian names, and conservation status has been developed; 86 species are listed as extremely rare and rare lichens in the Law on Natural Plants.

Research interests

- ✓ Research on education and popularization of diversity and functional characteristics, taxonomy, origin, ecosystem role, ecology, conservation and importance of lichenflora in Mongolia.
- ✓ Studies on the classification of air pollution by lichens, concentrations of pollutants, heavy metals, sulphur compounds, radioactive isotopes and elements, as well as spatial distribution of lichens using indicator species.
- ✓ Studies of the impact of climate, habitat fragmentation and grazing on the distribution and diversity of lichens, as well as assessment of species requiring conservation measures, extinction rates, ascription to species status and determination of status.
- ✓ Studies of the importance of lichen in terms of their use, including the extraction of new sources of organic acids, antioxidants and biologically active compounds with high antibacterial and antiviral properties from lichen and their use in pharmaceuticals, food and cosmetics industry.

Doctor (Ph.D) PUNSALDULAM Dashnyam

Laboratory of Microbial synthesis

Institute of Biology, Mongolian Academy of Sciences

e-mail: punsaldulam_d@mas.ac.mn**Academic Background**

Punsaldulam Dashnyam completed her Bachelor's and Master's degrees in Biotechnology and Biochemistry at the National University of Mongolia. She then earned her PhD in Biotechnology from the Institute of Biological Chemistry at Academia Sinica, Taiwan. Her doctoral research focused on the rational design of small-molecule inhibitors targeting gut bacterial enzymes, integrating enzymology and structural biology.

Currently, her research examines the impact of environment on soil microbial diversity and function, with a particular focus on understanding how microbial communities contribute to soil organic carbon storage and dynamics.

Research Interests

- ✓ Soil microbial diversity and function in response to climate change
- ✓ Contribution of soil microbial exopolymers to soil carbon stabilization
- ✓ Identification and application of indigenous microbial strains soil stabilization
- ✓ Microbial enzymes involved in xenobiotic degradation
- ✓ Bacterial exopolysaccharides as biosorbents

Doctor (Ph.D) ANASTASIA Vlasenko

Head of the Laboratory of Mycology, Algology and Lichenology

Central Siberian Botanical Garden of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences

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Academic Background

Anastasia Vlasenko received her Specialist degree in Economics of Environmental Management from Altai State University in 1999–2005. She then completed postgraduate studies at the V. L. Komarov Botanical Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (BIN RAS) from 2007 to 2010, defending her Candidate of Biological Sciences (PhD equivalent) thesis on “Myxomycetes (Myxomycetes) of pine forests of the right-bank part of the Upper Ob region.”

Over the course of her career, she has authored more than 100 scientific publications, including 75 journal articles (about 50 indexed in Web of Science and Scopus) and 2 monographs. She currently serves as Head of the Laboratory of Mycology, Algology and Lichenology at the Central Siberian Botanical Garden of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Sciences.

Research Interests

- ✓ Amoebozoa, diversity, ecology and biology of protists
- ✓ Taxonomy, systematics, and phylogeny of myxomycetes
- ✓ Biogeography, biota and biodiversity of myxomycetes, with a particular focus on Mongolia and Siberia
- ✓ DNA barcoding and molecular genetics of slime molds
- ✓ Application of myxomycetes and other protists in bioindication and environmental assessment
- ✓ Documentation, databasing and curation of myxomycete collections
- ✓ Integration of classical morphology and modern molecular approaches in the study of slime molds

Doctor (Ph.D) ULAMBAYAR Temuujin

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Academic Background

Ulambayar.T received her Ph.D from the Life science, Department of Plant Biotechnology, Hankyong National University, South Korea.

Research interests

- ✓ Molecular biology
- ✓ Gene engineering
- ✓ Plant biotechnology
- ✓ Molecular diagnostics
- ✓ Mutation

Doctor (Ph.D) LI JINZHUANG

Department of Food Technology
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and Technical College, Inner Mongolia
Agricultural University

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Academic Background

LI Jinzhuang Ph.D from the Mongolian University of Life Sciences in Mongolia.

Research interests

- ✓ Meat processing technology
- ✓ Microbial fermentation technology
- ✓ Nutritional diet research
- ✓ Patent technology commercialization

Master (M.Sc) UDAAKHBAYAR Jamchin
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Academic Background

Udaakhbayar is a Ph.D. candidate at the United Graduate School of Agricultural Sciences, Tottori University, Japan.

Research interests

- ✓ Diversity and community structure of fungi in Larix species
- ✓ Functional ecology of endophytic fungi in forest ecosystems
- ✓ Integration of culture-dependent and next-generation sequencing (NGS) approaches
- ✓ Plant growth-promoting mechanisms of fungi
- ✓ Soil–plant–microbe interactions
- ✓ Beneficial microorganism research

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Academic Background

Dulamsuren Khurelbataar graduated with a Bachelor's degree in Agricultural Biotechnology from the Mongolian University of Life Sciences in 2012 and completed a Master's degree at the same institution in 2014. Currently, She is a doctoral student at the university, specializing in mushroom biotechnology.

Research Interests

- ✓ Cultivation of edible and medicinal mushrooms
- ✓ Isolation of mycelium from wild mushrooms.

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Academic Background

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Research interests

- ✓ Soil fertility & microbial ecology
- ✓ Root–fungal interactions (AMF focus)
- ✓ Plant–microbe symbiosis
- ✓ Soil health in dryland systems
- ✓ Sustainable soil management
- ✓ Molecular analysis & bioinformatics
- ✓ Crop resilience & adaptation

Publications

✓ Mohammedali, A.K.H.*, Gorafi, Y.S.A., Kamal, N.M., Tahir, I.S.A., Tsujimoto, H., & Taniguchi, T. (2025). Exploring Genetic Variation in Root Traits and Root–Fungal Associations in *Aegilops tauschii*. *Agriculture*, 15(17), 1889.

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✓ Mohammedali, A.K.H.*, Kamal, N.M., Gorafi, Y.S.A., Tahir, I.S.A., Tsujimoto, H., & Taniguchi, T. (2025). Variation in Root Traits and Root–Endophyte Interactions in Primary Synthetic Wheat Derived from *Aegilops tauschii* Collected from Diverse Soil Types. *Agronomy*, 15(6), 1443.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy15061443>.

✓ Mohammedali, A.K.H.*, Musa, L.M.M., & Adlan, M.A.M. (2023). Occurrence and Diversity of Indigenous Mycorrhizal Fungi in Different Sudan Soils Using Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) as a Host Plant. *Chemical and Natural Resources Engineering Journal*, 7(1).

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Session I. RESEARCH OF MACROFUNGI**Screening of mycelial culture conditions for the growth of
*Agaricus arvensis***

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Abstract

Objective: To screen the optimal culture medium formulation for the mycelial growth of *Agaricus arvensis* providing a basis for cultivating high-quality strains and achieving large-scale production.

Methods

Using *Agaricus arvensis* strains a72, a99, and a100 as test materials the effects of different carbon sources (glucose, fructose sucrose, maltose, lactose, soluble starch corn starch, cellobios, mannose, nitrogen sources (peptone yeast powder yeast extract beef extract ammonium sulfate diammonium hydrogen phosphate beef powder, casein, glutamine), and pH values (4.5, 5.0, 5.5 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, 7.5, 8.0, 8.5) on mycelial growth rate colony vigor and growth index were investigated.

An orthogonal experiment with three-factor, three-level was conducted to determine the optimal culture medium formulation for mycelial growth.

Results

Sucrose was identified as the optimal carbon source for the mycelial growth of strains a72, a99, and a100, with growth rates of 2.84, 2.79, and 3.41 mm/d and growth indices of 11.360, 12.560 and 15.350, respectively. The optimal nitrogen source for strain a72 was glutamine with a growth rate of 3.43 mm/d and a growth index of 17.150, while diammonium hydrogen phosphate was optimal for strains a99 and a100, with growth rates of 4.19 and 3.85 mm/d and growth indices of 18.855 and 17.325, respectively.

The optimal pH value for mycelial growth of all three strains was 6.5. The three -factor three -level orthogonal experiment revealed that the optimal culture medium formulations were for strain a72, 25 g/L sucrose, 2.0 g/L glutamine pH 6.0; for strain a99, 25 g/L sucrose, 2.0 g/L diammonium hydrogen phosphate pH 6.0; and for strain a100 , 25 g/L sucrose, 2.5 g/L diammonium hydrogen phosphate pH 6.0.

Conclusion

The mycelial of *Agaricus arvensis* strains a72, a99, and a100 are more suitable for growth under slightly acidic to neutral environmental conditions. The three-factor three-level orthogonal experiment successfully identified optimal culture medium formulations for the mycelial growth of these strains.

Keywords: *Agaricus arvensis*, Mycelium, Carbon source, Nitrogen source, pH value, Growth rate, Growth index

Antioxidant activity of meat products fortified with *Pleurotus ostreatus*

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Abstract

Chemical and antioxidant activity of dried goat meat soup fortified with mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) were evaluated. The formulation of dried soup was developed, leveraging the natural antioxidant properties of mushrooms (0.7 mg GAE/g total phenolic content) to enhance product functionality. The phenolic content of product was 0.104 mg GAE/g, DPPH content of products was 22.83%. The TBARS values of the product at the storage of 3 months were 0.69 mg/kg. The moisture content of dried soup was 5.33%, protein 26.0%, fat 9.0%, ash 12.4% and total carbohydrate 47.3% respectively. Microbiological assessment showed that total bacterial counts remained below 10³ CFU/g throughout 56 days storage at 37°C, and for 6 months at room temperature. The results showed that mushroom-enriched dried meat soup could be a nutritional, safe product with shelflife stability.

Keywords: goat meat products; mushroom fortification; fatty acids; amino acids, antioxidant activity

Introduction

Consumers' perception and choice of food have been changing over the centuries. Modern consumers increasingly prioritize healthy and natural food options (Romano 2025). Processed meat and meat products are highly valued for their nutritional composition however, it

has been criticized due to their deficiency in vitamin C, dietary fibre, and antioxidants. Moreover, consumption of processed meats with high content of fat, saturated fatty acids, cholesterol, caloric content in several formulations, and synthetic additives is considered harmful to human health. The above reasons can significantly mitigate the risks, which can increase the risks of cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, gut issues, and other conditions related to obesity (Ruiz-Capillas and Herrero 2021; Das et al., 2021). Several studies have noted that mushroom fortification in meat products offers technological and health benefits. Mushrooms could provide an inexpensive source of bioactive substances, dietary fibers, antioxidants, and antimicrobial properties, which can improve the shelf life of meat products. Mushrooms have a low content of lipid, sodium and a unique flavor (Jayakumar et al., 2009) and enhancing the oxidative stability of the products by the supportive action of phenolic compounds, that can be used in various products as a substitute or additive (Manzi et al., 2000, Perez et al., 2021). The high antioxidant potential of oyster mushrooms can be utilized in applications as functional foods or nutraceuticals, thereby maintaining and promoting health benefits by combating oxidative stress and inflammation (Rosa et al., 2022; Shbeeb et al., 2019). Nevertheless, even with the current interest in the functional meat developments, there are very few investigations that focus on the interaction between oyster mushrooms and goat meat because the latter has a distinct fatty acid composition and is leaner than beef or lamb. This study aimed to examine the chemical and antioxidant activity of meat products added with mushrooms in different proportions to the formulation.

Materials and methods

Three-year-old Mongolian native goats (n=3) from Dundgovi province were slaughtered at the slaughterhouse. The goat carcasses were chilled and deboned. Meat samples were vacuum-packed and frozen at -18°C until subsequent analysis. Edible oyster mushrooms were obtained from “Mongolian mushrooms” plant where they were grown under controlled conditions at 22–25°C and 80–85% humidity. Mushrooms cut into 5 mm³ cubes. Bone broth was prepared by

simmering goat bones at 95°C for 2 h, after which diced meat and mushrooms were added and boiled continuously for 1 h. Starch was added and boiled for 5 min. The cooled soup was freeze-dried. Moisture content was measured via GB 5009.3–2016 standard. Fat content analyzed using the Soxhlet extraction method. Protein content was determined via the Kjeldahl method. Ash content was measured by GB 5009.4–2016. Total carbohydrates were calculated using the formula. Sodium content was determined via flame atomic absorption spectrometry GB 5009.91–2017. Total phenolic content was quantified using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, modified to reduce matrix interference from meat proteins, the absorbance measured at 765 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800). DPPH radical scavenging activity was evaluated to assess in vitro antioxidant capacity, with a protocol optimized for meat-mushroom blends. Lipid oxidation was assessed via the TBARS method, which quantifies malondialdehyde (MDA), a secondary product of lipid peroxidation. Microbiological analysis was carried out at the SAMO Institute, following ISO 4833-1:2013 standards.

Results and Discussion

This type of product was freeze-dried soup after heat-processed the seasoned goat meat and dried oyster mushrooms. A product intended for use by mixing with hot water that primarily designed for convenience, allowing for quick preparation without cooking. The mushroom fortified dried soup was developed with oyster mushroom proportions of 25%, 35%, and 50%. The dried soup with 25% mushrooms received the highest overall acceptability score (92/100) than others. Panelists noted that mushroom addition enhanced umami flavor, with the dried soup demonstrating the best balance of taste and texture (data not shown). The chemical composition of product showed in Table 1.

Table 1. Chemical composition of dried soup

Moisture, %	5.33
Total fat, %	9.0
Protein, %	26.0
Minerals (ash), %	12.4
Carbohydrate, %	47.3
Sodium, %	5.78
Energy, kJ/100g	1579

The moisture content was 5.33%, protein 26.0%, and fat 9.0% respectively. Dried soup had 47.3% carbohydrate content due to mushroom addition and starch addition for texture. Sodium levels were 5.78% in dried soup, reflecting differences in seasoning intensity and dehydration concentration. Drying significantly altered the composition. Freeze-drying removes moisture but retains other essential ingredients of the raw material, thus increasing the content of oil and other composition in the dry weight of the product (Bhat et al. 2021). Dried soup achieved a macronutrient distribution that aligns with the Acceptable Macronutrient Distribution Range (AMDR), making it a nutritionally complete alternative meal.

Table 2. Total phenolic content and antioxidant activity of product

Antioxidant activity	Dried <i>Pleurotus ostreatus</i>	Dried mushroom soup
Total phenolic content (mg GAE/g)	0.7	0.104
DPPH, free radical scavenging rate (%)	53.1	22.83
TBARS (mg/kg)	-	0.69

Dried oyster mushrooms had a total phenolic content of 0.7 mg GAE/g, with product showing 0.104mg GAE/g. Dried soup showed the 22.83% DPPH activity, possibly due to dilution during processing. After

3 months of storage, TBARS value was 0.69 mg/kg, well below the 1.0 mg/kg threshold for unacceptable lipid oxidation or indicating low lipid oxidation (Guillén-Sans & Guzmán-Chozas). These results confirm that mushroom addition contributes to antioxidant capacity, with formulation and processing methods influencing efficacy.

Microbiological stability and shelf life

The dried soup showed no detectable bacterial growth even at 6 months, attributed to its low moisture content. Microbiological assessment showed that total bacterial counts remained below 10^3 CFU/g throughout storage at 37°C, within 56 days, and at room temperature, counts stayed below 10^1 CFU/g for 6 months. This confirms that mushroom-enriched goat meat products maintain microbial stability, supporting their shelf-life stability for up to 6 months under proper storage conditions.

Conclusion

Antioxidant activity was also enhanced by mushroom fortification as indicated by the increase in DPPH scavenging values and decrease in TBARS indicating the ability of mushroom phenolics to provide protection on lipid oxidation. Microbiological evaluation of product showed that it could be stored up to six months under safe microbial limits and, therefore, as shelf-stable, value-added foods. The practical value of this stability is of importance to areas where the refrigeration facilities are limited and where there is seasonal food insecurity. Future studies can examine the acceptance of the consumer market and economic viability.

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Utilizing unused resources to cultivate mushrooms and create a regional recycling model

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Abstract

In the current food production system, a large amount of organic waste is generated and is mainly incinerated, resulting in huge costs and energy consumption (Ministry of the Environment (2020)). In this study, we clarified that food waste and food loss can be used for mushroom cultivation and developed a new mushroom culture medium to replace conventional sawdust. It was revealed that oyster mushrooms cultivated using food wastes as the main ingredient contain a high content of ergothioneine, which has a strong antioxidant effect. Mushrooms are a versatile food that is rich in dietary fiber, low in calories, and rich in protein, vitamins, and minerals, making them a food that can be enjoyed at the dinner table without getting tired of them.

Mushrooms have been loved by people all over the world since ancient times, and there are many types of mushrooms. The lignin-decomposing ability of white-rot fungi can also break down environmental pollutants such as dioxins (Takada et al., 1996). This powerful decomposition ability is the key to material circulation, and is a noteworthy ability that should be utilized in resource circulation. In this study, we demonstrated that mushrooms grown in a culture medium made primarily from food waste contain large amounts of ergothioneine, and further demonstrated that the ergothioneine concentration can be increased by cultivating mushrooms under blue LED irradiation.

Furthermore, we confirmed that ergothioneine is absorbed by plants, and found new possibilities for the effective use of waste culture medium that contains a large amount of ergothioneine and for the circulation of ergothioneine.

Ultimately, we would like to establish a regional circular food production system centered on mushroom cultivation using food residues and promote microcirculation.

Keywords: food waste; food loss; ergothioneine; Blue LED; *Pleurotus ostreatus*

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Screening of Liquid Culture Conditions for *Tricholoma mongolicum*

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Abstract

In this experiment, the *Tricholoma mongolicum* strain BM8090 was used as the test material. Single-factor and L9 (3⁴) orthogonal test methods were employed to investigate the effects of five different carbon sources (glucose, sucrose, maltose, soluble starch, lactose), five different nitrogen sources (peptone, yeast extract, glutamine, ammonium chloride, ammonium sulfate), and three different ratios of inorganic salts (KH₂PO₄ : MgSO₄ at 2:1, 1:1, 1:2) on the diameter and biomass of liquid-cultured *T. mongolicum* mycelial pellets.

The aim was to explore the liquid culture conditions and screen for a suitable culture medium formulation for its growth. The single-factor test results showed that the optimal carbon source for mycelial growth in the liquid spawn medium was glucose, the optimal nitrogen source was peptone, and the optimal inorganic salt ratio was 1:2.

The orthogonal test results indicated that the optimal culture medium formulation for *T. mongolicum* liquid spawn was glucose 15 g/L, peptone 2.5 g/L, KH₂PO₄ 0.25 g/L, and MgSO₄ 1 g/L, with the mycelial biomass reaching 1.113 mg/ml after 8 days of culture.

This study screened out a suitable culture medium formulation for the mycelial growth of *Tricholoma mongolicum* in liquid culture, providing a theoretical basis for enhancing strain viability, achieving artificial domestication, and enabling large-scale production.

Keywords: liquid inoculum; carbon and nitrogen sources; inorganic salts; biomass

Introduction

The growth process of edible fungi is influenced not only by environmental factors such as temperature, light, and humidity but also significantly by the nutritional composition of the culture substrate, which plays a critical role in mycelial growth and development, as well as the yield and quality of fruiting bodies. Similar to other microorganisms, edible fungi require essential nutrients such as carbon sources, nitrogen sources, inorganic salts, growth factors, and water for their growth and development. Among these, the carbon and nitrogen content, as well as the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio of the culture substrate, have particularly pronounced effects on their growth and development. *Tricholoma mongolicum* has complex requirements for its growth environment, and current research on its liquid culture conditions remains insufficient, with a lack of systematic studies on the effects of different carbon and nitrogen sources on its growth rate and vigor. This paper aims to investigate the effects of carbon and nitrogen nutrition to identify an optimal medium formulation for the liquid culture of *Tricholoma mongolicum*, thereby providing a theoretical reference for obtaining highly vigorous strains and advancing research on artificial domestication and cultivation.

Materials and Methods

Test Materials: The tested strains were provided by the Edible Mushroom Research Laboratory, Institute of Vegetables and Flowers, Inner Mongolia Academy of Agricultural and Animal Husbandry Sciences.

Test Methods

Test Medium: Liquid basal medium: potato 200 g/L, glucose 20 g/L, peptone 2 g/L, potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1 g/L, magnesium sulfate 0.5 g/L.

Experiments on Different Carbon and Nitrogen Sources and Inorganic Salts

Sucrose, maltose, soluble starch, and lactose containing the same carbon content as glucose in the basal medium were used to replace glucose, respectively. Yeast extract, glutamine, ammonium chloride, and ammonium sulfate containing the same nitrogen content as peptone in the basal medium were used to replace peptone, respectively.

Three concentration ratios of potassium dihydrogen phosphate to magnesium sulfate were set as follows: 1:2 (KH_2PO_4 0.5 g/L, MgSO_4 1 g/L), 1:1 (KH_2PO_4 1 g/L, MgSO_4 1 g/L), and 2:1 (KH_2PO_4 1 g/L, MgSO_4 0.5 g/L).

Indicator Measurement: Mycelial pellet diameter and biomass.

Results and Analysis

When glucose was used as the carbon source, the mycelial biomass was the highest at 0.94 mg/mL, followed by soluble starch. The effect on biomass in descending order was: glucose > soluble starch > lactose > sucrose > maltose. When peptone was used as the nitrogen source, the mycelial biomass was the highest at 0.98 mg/mL, followed by glutamine. The effect on biomass in descending order was: peptone > glutamine > ammonium sulfate > ammonium chloride > yeast extract.

When the inorganic salt ratio was 1:2, the mycelial biomass was the highest at 1.15 mg/mL. The effects of the three different inorganic salt ratios on biomass in descending order were: 1:2 > 1:1 > 2:1, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Effects of different carbon sources and inorganic salt ratios on the growth and development of *Tricholoma mongolicum*

Different factors	Carbon and nitrogen sources and inorganic salts	Biomass (mg/ml)	Diameter (mm)
Carbon source	Glucose	0.94±0.17 a	6.43
	Sucrose	0.42±0.01 bc	4.98
	Maltose	0.32±0.01 c	5.19
	Lactose	0.49±0.06 b	5.51
	Lactose	0.48±0.04 b	5.61
Nitrogen source	Peptone	0.98±0.08 a	5.95
	Yeast extract	0.72±0.12 b	6.23
	Glutamine	0.82±0.14 ab	6.08
	Ammonium chloride	0.76±0.09 b	6.27
	Ammonium sulfate	0.80±0.11 ab	6.78
Inorganic salt ratio	2:1	1	0.5
	1:1	1	1
	1:2	0.5	1

Note: Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences ($P < 0.05$).

An L9 (3^4) orthogonal experiment was conducted. The results showed that the order of factors affecting mycelial biomass was: potassium dihydrogen phosphate > peptone > magnesium sulfate > glucose. The relatively ideal medium formulation was glucose 15 g/L, peptone 2.5 g/L, potassium dihydrogen phosphate 0.5 g/L, and magnesium sulfate 1 g/L. After 8 days of culture, the mycelial biomass reached 1.113 mg/mL.

Table 2 Orthogonal Test Design: Factors and Levels (g/L)

Levels	Factors (g/L)			
	Carbon source (A)	Nitrogen source (B)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (C)	MgSO ₄ (D)
1	15	1.5	0.25	0.5
2	20	2	0.5	1
3	25	2.5	0.75	1.5

Table 3 Results of orthogonal experiment L₉ (3⁴)

No.	Factors (g/L)				Biomass (mg/ml)	Diameter (mm)
	Carbon source (A)	Nitrogen source (B)	KH ₂ PO ₄ (C)	MgSO ₄ (D)		
1	15 (1)	1.5 (1)	0.25 (1)	0.5 (1)	1.010	6.59
2	15 (1)	2.0 (2)	0.50 (2)	1.0 (2)	0.820	7.97
3	15 (1)	2.5 (3)	0.75 (3)	1.5 (3)	0.963	5.40
4	20 (2)	1.5 (1)	0.50 (2)	1.5 (1)	0.797	7.78
5	20 (2)	2.0 (2)	0.75 (3)	0.5 (1)	0.880	6.83
6	20 (2)	2.5 (3)	0.25 (1)	1.0 (2)	1.113	6.23
7	25 (1)	1.5 (1)	0.75 (3)	1.0 (2)	0.903	6.96
8	25 (3)	2.0 (2)	0.25 (1)	1.5 (3)	0.973	7.95
9	25 (3)	2.5 (3)	0.50 (2)	0.5 (1)	0.843	7.03
K1	0.931	0.903	1.032	0.911	0.931	
K2	0.930	0.891	0.820	0.946	0.930	
K3	0.907	0.973	0.916	0.911	0.907	
R	0.024	0.082	0.212	0.035	0.024	
Order						
C > B > D > A						
Optimal level						
A ₁		B ₃		C ₁		D ₂

Optimal combination

A₁ B₃ C₁ D₂

Discussion and Conclusion: This study has found that there is no significant linear correlation between mycelial pellet diameter and biomass. In the nitrogen source experiment, the peptone treatment group exhibited the highest biomass but the smallest pellet diameter; in the inorganic salt experiment, the group with the highest biomass did not have the largest pellet diameter either. This may be attributed to the influence of multiple factors on pellet size, such as medium viscosity, shaker speed, and mycelial aggregation tendency, which requires further investigation.

Taxonomic overview of psychoactive-associated mushroom genera in Mongolia

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Abstract

Here we provide a concise taxonomic synthesis of mushroom genera recorded from Mongolia that include psychoactive representatives worldwide. Based on published checklists and recent taxonomic revisions, we summarize the occurrence of *Amanita*, *Panaeolus*, *Gymnopilus*, *Protostropharia*, and related taxa, and evaluate the current level of evidence for psychoactive potential. As a case study, we briefly incorporate our recently described species, *Gymnopilus poaceophilus*, a phylogenetically distinct taxon from Mongolian grasslands whose psychoactive status remains unknown. This short communication highlights key taxonomic gaps and emphasizes the need for integrative approaches combining morphology, DNA barcoding, and chemical profiling in future studies.

Keywords: fungal biodiversity, psychoactive fungi, taxonomy, Mongolia, species inventory

Introduction

Psychoactive mushrooms are fungi capable of producing compounds that affect the central nervous system, most notably psilocybin, psilocin, muscimol, and ibotenic acid. These compounds

are primarily associated with several basidiomycete genera, including *Psilocybe*, *Panaeolus*, *Gymnopilus*, and *Amanita*. While psychoactive fungi have been well documented in Europe, North America, and parts of Asia, data from Mongolia are fragmentary and largely incidental.

Existing mycological studies in Mongolia have focused mainly on edible, medicinal, and toxic mushrooms, with psychoactive species rarely treated as a distinct research subject. As a result, their taxonomic status, distribution, and biodiversity remain poorly understood. The main research problem addressed in this communication is the lack of synthesized taxonomic information on psychoactive mushrooms occurring in Mongolia.

Materials and Methods

This study is based on a qualitative taxonomic analysis of species records included in a comprehensive fungal species list compiled from Mongolian mycological surveys. Species belonging to genera known to contain psychoactive taxa were extracted and reviewed. Taxonomic nomenclature follows current international standards, with attention given to recent generic revisions (e.g., *Psilocybe* vs. *Deconica*, *Stropharia* vs. *Protostropharia*).

No experimental or molecular analyses were conducted; instead, emphasis was placed on literature-based taxonomy and species occurrence records. The structure and format of this manuscript follow the official guidelines for short original communications of the Mycology IV International Scientific Conference.

Results

The reviewed species list confirms the occurrence of several genera that include psychoactive mushrooms. Notable examples include *Amanita muscaria* and *Amanita pantherina*, which are known for containing muscimol and ibotenic acid. Species of *Panaeolus* (e.g., *Panaeolus papilionaceus*, *P. semiovatus*) and *Protostropharia* (*Protostropharia semiglobata*) were also recorded, genera that are globally associated with psilocybin-producing taxa.

In addition, representatives of *Gymnopilus* (e.g., *Gymnopilus aeruginosus*, *G. penetrans*) were identified. Although not all species within these genera are psychoactive, their presence indicates a taxonomic and ecological potential for psychoactive diversity within Mongolia (Table 1).

Table 1. Psychoactive-associated mushrooms recorded from Mongolia: global evidence and local testing status

No	Species (recorded in Mongolia)	Compound(s) reported globally	Key references (global evidence)
1	<i>Amanita muscaria</i>	Muscimol; ibotenic acid	Gonmori et al. (2012); Poliwoda et al. (2014)
2	<i>Amanita pantherina</i>	Muscimol; ibotenic acid	Stříbrný et al. (2011); Poliwoda et al. (2014)
3	<i>Gymnopilus aeruginosus</i>	Psilocybin (reported); psilocin (via hydrolysis context)	Hatfield & Valdes (1978)
4	<i>Panaeolus semiovatus</i>	Psilocybin (reported in <i>Panaeolus</i> literature; species-level evidence varies by source)	Strauss et al. (2023); He et al. (2026)
5	<i>Panaeolus papilionaceus</i>	Psilocybin (reported, but “producing” vs “non-producing” documented across specimens)	He et al. (2026)
6	<i>Gymnopilus liquiritiae</i>	Psilocybin: conflicting claims across secondary sources	Strauss et al. (2022)
7	<i>Gymnopilus poaceophilus</i>	Unknown (no chemical data published)	Cheng et al. (2026)
8	<i>Gymnopilus penetrans</i>	Psilocybin: genus-level association; species-level evidence inconsistent across literature	Strauss et al. (2022)
9	<i>Psilocybe coronilla</i>	Psilocybin: not reliably supported for this taxon; taxonomic/nomenclatural confusion with <i>Stropharia</i>	Strauss et al. (2022)

		<i>coronilla</i> in secondary sources	
10	<i>Protostropharia semiglobata</i>	Psilocybin: not confirmed here; confusion risk with coprophilous psychoactive taxa in dung habitats	Wang & Tzean (2015); Liu et al. (2025)

Discussion and Conclusion

The results demonstrate that Mongolia hosts multiple fungal genera with known psychoactive representatives, suggesting that psychoactive mushrooms are a natural component of the country's fungal biodiversity. However, the absence of molecular confirmation and targeted chemical analyses limits precise identification of psychoactive species.

Recent integrative taxonomic work added *Gymnopilus poaceophilus* sp. nov. to the Mongolian mycobiota. Although the genus *Gymnopilus* includes species with confirmed psilocybin production, the new species is currently known only from morphological and ITS+LSU phylogenetic evidence, forming a strongly supported monophyletic lineage sister to *G. aeruginosus* and allied taxa. No chemical analyses have been conducted, and its psychoactive status therefore remains unknown. The discovery highlights the importance of integrative taxonomy as a prerequisite for evaluating psychoactive potential in Mongolian fungi.

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Optimization of Liquid Spawn Culture Medium Formulation for *Pleurotus citrinopileatus*

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Abstract

Liquid spawn is one of the key technologies in the modern industrialized production of edible fungi. Compared with traditional solid spawn, it offers significant advantages in terms of production cost, production cycle, uniformity of mycelial age, inoculation efficiency, and adaptability to automation. The quality of liquid spawn is highly dependent on the composition of the culture medium. An appropriate formulation can effectively promote the formation of high-quality mycelial pellets, which is an important foundation for ensuring spawn vitality, shortening the cultivation cycle, and achieving high and stable yields. To improve the quality of liquid spawn of *Pleurotus citrinopileatus*, this study systematically investigated the effects of carbon sources (glucose, sucrose, maltose, fructose, soluble starch, lactose, xylose), nitrogen sources (yeast extract powder, peptone, ammonium sulfate, cysteine, methionine, urea, ammonium tartrate), and inorganic salts (potassium dihydrogen phosphate, magnesium sulfate) on the mycelial pellet density, diameter, and biomass (dry weight) of *P.citrinopileatus* liquid spawn using single-factor comparative analysis and orthogonal experimental design. The single-factor experiments identified the optimal types and concentrations of carbon and nitrogen sources, with glucose being the most suitable carbon source at a concentration of 25 g·L⁻¹ and yeast extract powder as the optimal nitrogen source at a concentration of 5 g·L⁻¹. Based on the single-factor experiments, an L₉(3⁴) orthogonal experimental design was employed, and the results indicated that the optimal liquid

spawn culture medium formula for *P. citrinopileatus* consisted of glucose at 25 g·L⁻¹, yeast extract powder at 5 g·L⁻¹, potassium dihydrogen phosphate at 0.5 g·L⁻¹, and magnesium sulfate at 0.8 g·L⁻¹. Under this formula, the liquid spawn of *P. citrinopileatus* exhibited uniformly distributed mycelial pellet diameters and the highest biomass dry weight. This formula provides a reliable theoretical basis and technical reference for the large-scale and efficient production of *P. citrinopileatus* liquid spawn.

Keywords: Mycelial pellet density; mycelial pellet diameter; mycelial pellet biomass; single-factor experiment; orthogonal experiment

Introduction

Pleurotus citrinopileatus is an edible fungus with both nutritional and medicinal value. It is rich in high-quality protein, bioactive polysaccharides, various minerals, and essential amino acids for the human body [1]. This fungus has a wide environmental adaptability, short growth cycle, high yield, and significant potential for industrial chain expansion. Therefore, this study aims to systematically optimize the culture medium formulation for liquid spawn of *P. citrinopileatus*. Through single-factor comparative analysis, the optimal type and concentration of carbon and nitrogen sources were screened. On this basis, an orthogonal experimental design was employed to optimize the concentration ratios of key components, using mycelial pellet biomass as the core evaluation indicator, and mycelial pellet density and diameter as auxiliary indicators, to identify the optimal medium combination. This study seeks to provide a reliable theoretical basis and practical guidance for the standardized preparation and efficient propagation of high-quality liquid spawn of *P. citrinopileatus*, thereby supporting its industrial development.

Materials and Methods

The tested strain was *P. citrinopileatus* cultivar "Meng Yuhuanggu No.1", preserved at the Edible Fungus Industrialization Engineering Center of Inner Mongolia Academy of Agricultural and Animal Husbandry Sciences.

Instruments used: one-thousandth balance, oven, clean bench, constant temperature shaking incubator (Licheng Instrument Technology Co Ltd), fully automatic high-pressure steam sterilizer, incubator, refrigerator. PDA culture medium: potato 200 g, glucose 10 g, sucrose 10 g, peptone 1.8 g, yeast powder 1.8 g, magnesium sulfate 0.5 g, potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1 g, agar 10 g, distilled water 1 L, pH 6.0~7.0.

Basal liquid culture medium: potato 200 g, glucose 20 g, peptone 5 g, magnesium sulfate 0.5 g, potassium dihydrogen phosphate 1 g, distilled water 1 L, pH 6.0~7.0.

Different carbon source concentrations were set at 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 g · L⁻¹, and different nitrogen source concentrations were set at 1, 3, 5, 7, and 9 g · L⁻¹, with three biological replicates for each treatment. The prepared liquid media were dispensed into 150 mL conical flasks, 100 mL per flask, and sterilized in an autoclave. Five mycelial blocks were inoculated into each flask and incubated in a shaking incubator at 180 r/min and 25 °C for 7 days. Subsequently, the mycelial pellets were separated from the liquid, and the mycelial pellet biomass was measured.

Mycelial pellet density and mycelial pellet diameter were recorded according to the method of Zhou [2]. Mycelial pellet biomass was determined following the method of Hu [3]. Mycelial pellet biomass (g · L⁻¹) was calculated as dry weight of mycelial pellets (g) / volume of liquid culture (L). Based on the optimal carbon and nitrogen sources determined from the single-factor experiments, combined with potassium dihydrogen phosphate and magnesium sulfate, an L9 (3⁴) orthogonal experimental design with four factors and three levels was adopted (Table 1). Each group had three replicates, and the dry weight of mycelial pellets was measured, with the average value taken.

Table 1 Factor levels for the orthogonal array L₉(3⁴) design in liquid culture medium formula.

Level	Concentration/ (g · L ⁻¹)
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	Carbon sources	Nitrogen sources	KH ₂ PO ₄	MgSO ₄
1	20	3	0.3	0.4
2	25	5	0.5	0.6
3	30	7	0.7	0.8

Results

The optimal carbon source was glucose at a concentration of 25 g·L⁻¹, and the optimal nitrogen source was yeast extract powder at a concentration of 5 g·L⁻¹.

Range analysis revealed that the optimal formulation for the liquid culture medium of *P.citrinopileatus* was glucose at 25 g·L⁻¹, yeast extract powder at 5 g·L⁻¹, potassium dihydrogen phosphate at 0.5 g·L⁻¹, and magnesium sulfate at 0.8 g·L⁻¹.

Discussion and Conclusion

Due to differences in their chemical structures, metabolic pathways, and osmotic pressure effects, various carbon sources exhibit distinct optimal concentrations and patterns of mycelial pellet development. When the carbon source is sufficient, a large number of mycelial pellets form, but individual pellets tend to be smaller; when the carbon source is insufficient, the number of pellets decreases, but individual pellets become larger. Gao ^[4] also identified glucose as the optimal carbon source in their study on liquid spawn of *P.citrinopileatus*, which is consistent with the findings of this paper.

Complex organic nitrogen sources (such as yeast extract powder and peptone) show significant advantages, while inorganic ammonium salts and simple organic nitrogen sources are less effective, and single amino acid nitrogen sources have limited effects. Nitrogen sources also regulate the balance between pellet quantity and individual size. Most nitrogen sources have an optimal concentration; concentrations exceeding this optimum inhibit the formation of new pellets and reduce pellet density. Yeast extract powder was identified as the optimal nitrogen source, yielding relatively high biomass.

Using mycelial pellet biomass as the evaluation indicator, this study optimized the formulation of the liquid fermentation medium for

P.citrinopileatus through orthogonal experiments. The optimal medium composition was determined as glucose 25 g·L⁻¹, yeast extract powder 5 g·L⁻¹, potassium dihydrogen phosphate 0.5 g·L⁻¹, and magnesium sulfate 0.8 g·L⁻¹.

This medium formulation has a well-defined composition and is simple to prepare, providing a reliable technical approach for the industrial shake-flask propagation of *P.citrinopileatus* liquid spawn. Additionally, it lays a process foundation and offers a theoretical reference for large-scale fermentation cultivation, mycelial mass production, and the development of related bioactive metabolites.

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Conservation and Protection of Mongolian Fungal Genetic Resources (Fungal Gene Bank)

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Abstract

Fungal genetic resources consist of diverse, dried specimens, mother cultures (strains), gene and genomic data used for research in medicine, agriculture, and biotechnology. Mongolian law on genetic resources regulates the access, utilization, conservation, and benefit-sharing of genetic material from plants, fungus, animals, and microorganisms and pointed out the importance of establishing a gene pool. Therefore, the Botanical Garden and Research Institute of the Mongolian Academy of Sciences is working to establish a Natural Plant Genetic Resources Sub-fund and a Mushroom Genetic Resources Sub-fund. The further studies are required the propagation of economic plants and mushrooms, the assessment of rarity status for flora and fungus, and the implementation of in-situ and ex-situ conservation strategies for endangered and rare species.

Keywords: Fungi, GenBank, genetic resources, herbarium, conservation and protection, Mongolia

Introduction

important resource that is self-renewable in nature, no less than Mongolia's minerals and mineral resources, is biodiversity. The

Mongolian genetic resources, which are highly nutritious and have a unique ability to overcome and withstand disease, drought, cold, and harsh conditions, are a unique and valuable asset in the world.

Fungi are not only food and medicine for humans, but they also play a huge role in nature. Specifically, 115 species of agaricoid mushroom grow in the Mongolian forest and form mycorrhizae in symbiosis with trees. Mycorrhizal fungi obtain organic substances, such as carbon and vitamins, from the tree. In exchange, the tree absorbs water and dissolved minerals—including potassium, calcium, and phosphorus—thanks to the fungus's extensive mycelial network. Saprophytic fungi decompose lignin and cellulose. Mycelium of fungi spreads through the soil humus layer (zone A1), enriching the soil with nitrogen. Mushrooms are of great benefit to humans through their medicinal and nutritional value, and to the environment through their ability to decompose organic residues of plants and animals. Despite these many benefits, they can also cause diseases in humans, animals, and plants (Borman et al., 2008).

Due to global climate change, desertification, and human activities, Mongolian fungi and lichen species are rapidly becoming rare. The first assessment of fungus species in Mongolia using IUCN Red List criteria was conducted in 2018, followed by subsequent assessments in 2020, 2022 and 2025. Approximately 95 species have been assessed at the regional level using IUCN categories and criteria (Kherlenchimeg and Burenbaatar 2022). Currently, we plan to include 19 species in the new list of "Very Rare Fungi of Mongolia", and 32 species in the list of "Rare Fungi of Mongolia". In the Red Book of Mongolia (2013), one species (*Leucocalocybe Mongolia*) was registered as "Very Rare" and 12 species as "Rare".

Mushrooms are a key factor in soil fertility and tree growth (mycorrhiza), as well as valuable raw materials for medical and agricultural biotechnology. However, the current lack of a system for preserving genetic resources and a standard laboratory base poses a risk of losing natural.

Results and Discussion

Current status of conservation of fungal genetic resources in Mongolia: As of 2017, 631 species of higher fungi belonging to 88 families and 237 genera were recorded in the Mongolian mushroom province. In 2024, we updated and revised the checklist of macrofungi, along with the distribution of phytogeographical regions and the regional conservation status in Mongolia. The checklist now comprises 677 macrofungal species belonging to 284 genera and 119 families in the country.

G.Uranchimeg was conducting taxonomic research on higher fungi in Mongolia since 1998 and has established a Fungal Herbarium containing about 500 samples from a collection of more than 250 species of fungi. Over the past 40 years, samples of 3,250 natural fungi (79% of the total species) have been preserved in dried form in the Herbarium Fund of the Mushroom and Lichen Genetic Resources Branch (FUBA) of the Sector of Fungi and Lichen Genetic Resources, Botanic Garden and Research Institute, Mongolian Academy of Sciences.

In 2011, with the support of the Ministry of Nature and Environment, a feasibility study was conducted to establish a Mongolian Natural Plant Gene Bank at the Botanical Garden. In 2013, based on this research, the design and budget for the construction of the Genebank were prepared, at the Botanic Garden. In 2025, at the initiative of the President of Mongolia, U.Khurelsukh, the Unified Complex of Scientific Institutes was built, and this year the laboratory building was put into operation. The NATURAL PLANT AND FUNGI GENBANK has moved into a room with an area of 1494.5 m² for offices, laboratories, and herbarium funds.

Fungal genetic resources consist of diverse, dried specimens, mother cultures (strains), gene and genomic data used for research in medicine, agriculture, and biotechnology.

Mongolian law on genetic resources regulates the access, utilization, conservation, and benefit-sharing of genetic material from plants, fungus, animals, and microorganisms and pointed out the importance of establishing a gene pool. Therefore, the Botanical Garden and Research Institute of the Mongolian Academy of Sciences

is working to establish a Natural Plant Genetic Resources Sub-fund and a Mushroom Genetic Resources Sub-fund. The Mushroom Genetic Resources Sub-fund of the Mushroom and Lichen Genetic Resources Branch has the following structure.

- 2.5.3. Pathogenic Fungi;
- 2.6.1. Collections of Fungi and Lichens (Herbarium);
- 2.6.2. Mother culture of Fungi and Lichens;
- 2.6.3. Pure culture of Fungi and Lichens;
- 2.6.4. DNA of Fungi and Lichens (deoxyribonucleic acid);

The Importance of Establishing a Gene Bank: Establishing a gene bank is important for our country, which has a unique and fragile ecosystem. Protecting Mongolia's fungal genetic resources will have a positive impact on ecosystem stability, food security, and national security.

- If a species becomes extinct in the wild, the stored seeds or DNA can be used to reintroduce it into its natural environment.
- It will serve as a significant catalyst for developing import-substituting industries and transforming the country into a food exporter.
- In the event of large-scale environmental disasters (such as massive forest fires or mining-related land degradation), a Gene Bank provides the specific, locally-adapted seeds needed for high-success reforestation and land rehabilitation.

A Gene Bank is not just a storage facility; it is an active research hub. Therefore, to address the challenges inherent in establishing a gene bank:

- It is essential to enhance laboratory capacities through the provision of standardized equipment and advanced methodologies, alongside a comprehensive technological modernization.
- Furthermore, strengthening human capital by expanding workforce numbers and addressing remuneration structures remains a primary strategic priority.

Conclusion

Current research focuses on establishing standardized protocols for these sub-funds and ensuring the long-term operational sustainability of the gene bank.

The further studies are required the propagation of economic plants and mushrooms, the assessment of rarity status for flora and fungus, and the implementation of in-situ and ex-situ conservation strategies for endangered and rare species.

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**Combining Transcriptome and Metabolome Analyzed
Differentially Expressed Genes and Differential Metabolites in
Development Period of Caoyuanheimo-1 (*Agaricus* sp.) from
Inner Mongolia, China**

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Abstract:

Caoyuanheimo-1 (*Agaricus* sp.) is a delectable mushroom native to Inner Mongolia, China, belonging to the *Agaricus* genus and valued for both its edible and medicinal properties. Although it has been cultivated to a certain extent, the molecular mechanisms regulating its development remain poorly understood. Building on our understanding of its growth and development conditions at various stages, we conducted transcriptomic and metabolomic studies to identify the differentially expressed genes (DEGs) and metabolites throughout its growth cycle.

Simultaneously, we analyzed the synthesis pathways and identified several key genes involved in the production of terpenoids, which are secondary metabolites with medicinal value widely found in mushrooms. A total of 6843 unigenes were annotated, and 449 metabolites were detected in our study. Many of these metabolites and differentially expressed genes (DEGs) are involved in the synthesis and metabolism of amino acids, such as arginine, cysteine, methionine, and other amino acids, which indicates that the genes related to amino acid metabolism may play an important role in the fruiting body development of Caoyuanheimo-1. Succinic acid also showed a significant positive correlation with the transcriptional level changes of nine genes, including laccase-1 (TRINITY_DN5510_c0_g1), fruiting

body protein SC3 (TRINITY_DN3577_c0_g1), and zinc-binding dihydrogenase (TRINITY_DN2099_c0_g1), etc. Additionally, seventeen terpenoids and terpenoid-related substances were identified, comprising five terpenoid glycosides, three monoterpenoids, two diterpenoids, one sesquiterpenoid, one sesterterpenoid, two terpenoid lactones, and three triterpenoids. The expression levels of the genes related to terpenoid synthesis varied across the three developmental stages.

Keywords: primordium period; fruiting body period; synthesis pathways; terpenoids

Introduction

The Prairie Brown Mushroom, commonly known as Caoyuanheimo, belongs to the genus *Agaricus* and is a delectable mushroom growing in the grasslands of Xilingol League, Inner Mongolia¹. Its taxonomic status is controversial, with morphological observations suggesting a close relationship to *Agaricus bisporus*. Due to diminishing wild resources, a domesticated strain, "Caoyuanheimo-1," has been developed.

The transition from vegetative mycelial growth to reproductive growth (primordium formation) is a critical phase in the life cycle of edible fungi. However, the genetic and molecular mechanisms regulating the development of Caoyuanheimo-1 are not well understood. Transcriptomics and metabolomics are effective tools for uncovering these mechanisms¹. Therefore, this study aimed to systematically analyze the differentially expressed genes and metabolites across different developmental stages of Caoyuanheimo-1, with a particular focus on the biosynthesis pathways of medicinally valuable terpenoids², to clarify the molecular basis of its growth and development.

Materials and Methods

Sample Preparation

Samples were collected from three developmental stages of cultivated *Caoyuanheimo-1*: the primordium period (HY, diameter <1 cm), the young fruiting body period (HZ, cap diameter 4.5–5.0 cm), and the ripe fruiting body period (HC, cap diameter 7.5–8.5 cm). Three independent biological samples were selected for repeated experiments at each developmental period, with a total of nine samples tested.

Metabolomics Analysis

Untargeted metabolite profiling was performed using a UHPLC-MS/MS system. Principal component analysis (PCA) and orthogonal partial least squares-discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA) were conducted using SIMCA software. Differentially accumulated metabolites (DAMs) were screened with criteria of variable importance in projection (VIP) > 1 from the OPLS-DA model and a p-value < 0.05 from Student's t-test. Metabolites were annotated using the HMDB and KEGG databases.

Transcriptomics Analysis

An NEBNextR Ultra™ Direct RNA Library Prep Kit was used with IlluminaR (NEB, USA) for library construction. Clean reads were aligned to a reference genome using HISAT2. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were identified using DESeq2 with thresholds of adjusted p-value < 0.01 and absolute value of log₂(fold change) > 1. KEGG pathway enrichment analysis was performed using KOBAS.

Correlation Analysis

Spearman correlation analysis was performed between the top 50 genes with the lowest false discovery rate (FDR) from the transcriptome and the top 50 metabolites with the highest VIP values from the metabolomics data, followed by visualization.

Results

Metabolomic analysis detected 449 metabolites. Comparing HY vs. HZ, 11 DAMs were found, with nine (including DL-dopa and pyruvic acid) significantly increased in HZ. Comparing HY vs. HC, 16 DAMs were identified, with 14 (including 5Z-dodecenoic acid and succinic acid) significantly increased in HC. Comparing HZ vs. HC, 12 DAMs were found. Nicotinic acid, urocanic acid, folinic acid, and glutathione were identified as differential metabolites in the primordium period.

Transcriptome assembly yielded 50,303 transcripts and 8,208 unigenes. Among them, 6,843 unigenes were annotated, and 96.43% of the annotated unigenes matched sequences of *Agaricus bisporus*. DEG analysis revealed 505, 181, and 361 DEGs in the HY vs. HC, HZ vs. HC, and HY vs. HZ comparisons, respectively. These DEGs were significantly enriched in pathways such as protein processing in the endoplasmic reticulum, phenylalanine metabolism, the MAPK signaling pathway, and terpenoid backbone biosynthesis.

Correlation analysis showed significant correlations between metabolite levels and transcriptional changes of multiple genes. For example, succinic acid was positively correlated with nine genes, including laccase-1 (TRINITY_DN5510_c0_g1). The carboxypeptidase S gene (TRINITY_DN96_c0_g1) and ten other genes showed consistently upregulated transcriptional levels from HY to HC.

Seventeen terpenoids and related substances were identified. The contents of two terpenoid precursors, pyruvic acid and methyl glutaric acid, increased significantly during HZ and HC. Concurrently, the transcriptional levels of key terpenoid biosynthesis genes, such as DXS (1-deoxy-D-xylulose-5-phosphate synthase), increased significantly in HZ and HC, while GGPPS (geranylgeranyl diphosphate synthase) and GPPS (geranyl diphosphate synthase) levels increased in HZ and decreased to basal levels in HC.

Discussion and Conclusion

This study presents the first multi-omics analysis of *Caoyuanheimo-1* across three key developmental stages. Analysis of DAMs and DEGs suggests that genes and pathways related to amino acid metabolism may play a significant role in its fruiting body

development, consistent with findings in *A. bisporus*. Correlation analysis revealed strong associations between specific metabolites (e.g., succinic acid) and key developmental genes (e.g., those encoding laccase and hydrophobin), providing clues for understanding the synergistic regulation of metabolism and gene expression.

The upregulation of precursor contents and related gene (DXS, GGPPS, GPPS) expression during fruiting body development suggests that terpenoid biosynthesis in Caoyuanheimo-1 may be closely linked to fruiting body maturation, providing a molecular basis for exploring its medicinal value. The high transcriptome sequence match to *A. bisporus* also offers a reference for clarifying its taxonomy. In summary, this study systematically reveals the dynamic landscape of gene expression and metabolite accumulation during the growth and development of Caoyuanheimo-1, laying a theoretical foundation for subsequent genetic breeding, cultivation regulation, and bioactive component development of this rare edible mushroom.

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Research on Wild Mushrooms in Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

Sindh, Pakistan, possesses a diverse range of ecological zones that support the growth of various wild mushroom species. This study aims to document the diversity, distribution, and potential uses of wild mushrooms found in different regions of Sindh. Field surveys were conducted across forests, agricultural lands, and wetland ecosystems. The findings highlight the presence of several edible and medicinal mushroom species, emphasizing their ecological and economic importance. The study suggests further research for sustainable utilization and conservation of fungal biodiversity in the region.

Keywords: Wild Mushrooms, Sindh, Fungal Diversity, Edible Mushrooms, Medicinal Fungi

Introduction

Mushrooms, belonging to the kingdom fungi, play a crucial role in ecosystem functioning as decomposers and nutrient recyclers. In Pakistan, particularly in Sindh, wild mushrooms are largely underexplored despite their ecological and medicinal significance. Rural communities have traditionally used certain species for food and medicine. This study focuses on exploring wild mushroom diversity in Sindh and documenting their potential benefits.

Study Area and Methodology

Field surveys were conducted in various districts of Sindh, including forest areas, riverine belts, and agricultural lands during the monsoon season. Mushroom specimens were collected, photographed, and preserved. Identification was carried out based on morphological characteristics and available taxonomic literature. Local

knowledge was also considered to identify edible and medicinal species.

Results and Discussion

The study documented more than 40–50 species of wild mushrooms belonging to different genera. Commonly identified genera include *Termitomyces*, *Agaricus*, and *Ganoderma*. Several species were found to be edible, while others showed potential medicinal properties such as antimicrobial and antioxidant activity. However, lack of awareness and proper identification poses risks of toxic mushroom consumption. The diversity observed indicates that Sindh has favorable conditions for mushroom growth, especially during the rainy season. There is significant potential for promoting mushroom cultivation and sustainable harvesting.

Conclusion

Wild mushrooms in Sindh represent an important yet underutilized natural resource. They have ecological, nutritional, and medicinal value. There is a need for further scientific research, public awareness, and conservation strategies to utilize this resource sustainably and safely.

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Investigation of *Inonotus hispidus* in Mongolia and metabolic composition differences between mycelium and fruiting bodies with metabolic method

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Abstract

Inonotus hispidus is a medicinal basidiomycete that synthesizes diverse secondary metabolites with ecological and pharmacological relevance. Here, we report the first confirmed occurrence of *I. hispidus* in Mongolia and present a non-targeted LC–MS metabolomic comparison between mycelium and fruiting bodies. Field collections from Selenge province were taxonomically authenticated (voucher UBA 2212190). LC–MS detected 4,528 metabolites, with 2,629 differentially expressed under stringent criteria. Multivariate analyses (PCA; PLS-DA) showed clear stage separation (PC1 \approx 58%; PLS-DA $R^2Y = 1.00$; $Q^2 \approx 0.96$ – 0.97). Mycelium was enriched in defensive alkaloids, antioxidants, and primary-energy intermediates, alongside lipid-signaling molecules; fruiting bodies accumulated flavonoids/phenolics, structural glycans, nucleosides for RNA turnover, and polyketide-linked toxicants. KEGG/GSEA highlighted phenylpropanoid/flavonoid and tryptophan/tyrosine routes in fruiting bodies, versus glycolysis/TCA and fatty-acid pathways in mycelium. These results clarify developmental metabolic reprogramming in *I. hispidus*, expand its biogeography to Mongolia, and frame opportunities for pharmacology and safe bioprocessing.

Keywords: *Inonotus hispidus*; LC–MS metabolomics; mycelium; fruiting body;

Introduction

Fungal secondary metabolites (phenolics, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids) underpin ecological defense, signaling, and prospective therapeutic activities (Zenkov et al., 2016; Wink, 2010, 2015; Harborne, 2014). *Inonotus hispidus* is recognized among medicinal fungi in East Asia for such bioactivity (Dai et al., 2009; Moore et al., 2020). Despite broad Eurasian distribution, no Mongolian record existed until the present survey in Selenge province (Yeroo River, *Salix* host).

Developmental stage strongly shapes fungal chemistry: mycelium emphasizes resource acquisition/defense, and fruiting bodies emphasize pigmentation, structure, and sporulation (Moore et al., 2020; Beccaccioli & Marzia, 2019). We therefore coupled ecological documentation with LC–MS–based, non-targeted metabolomics to resolve stage-specific biochemical programs in *I. hispidus*.

Materials and Methods

Field and taxonomy. Specimens were collected in Khuder, Selenge; macromorphology/microscopy matched *I. hispidus* and voucher UBA 2212190 was deposited.

Samples. Group A: cultured mycelia (n = 6); Group B: fruiting bodies (n = 6).

Extraction & LC–MS. Methanol:acetonitrile (1:1), cold precipitation, vacuum drying, reconstitution; acquisition in positive/negative ion modes.

Processing & statistics. ProteoWizard → XCMS (peak picking, RT correction, filtering); in-house library matching; PCA/PLS-DA; differential criteria $VIP > 1.0$, $FC > 1.5 / < 0.667$, $P < 0.05$. Pathway analysis by KEGG enrichment (hypergeometric) and GSEA (FDR < 0.05) (GSEA Overview, 2024).

Results and Discussion

Global features. LC–MS detected 4,528 metabolites (POS 2,699; NEG 1,829); 2,629 were differential (POS 1,561; NEG 1,068). PCA separated stages (PC1 \approx 58%); PLS-DA achieved $R^2Y = 1.00$ and $Q^2 \approx 0.96$ – 0.97 , indicating robust discrimination.

Class-level landscape. Nine major classes dominated (lipids, organic acids, organoheterocycles, organic oxygen compounds, phenylpropanoids/polyketides, benzenoids, nucleotides, alkaloids, organic nitrogen compounds). Functional assignments are consistent with known fungal biochemistry: membranes/signaling (lipids), energy and TCA flux (organic acids), indole/purine signaling (organoheterocycles), structural/energy carbohydrates (organic oxygen compounds) (Fernie et al., 2004; Moore et al., 2020; Beccaccioli & Marzia, 2019). The mycelium skewed toward energy/defense; the fruiting bodies toward pigmentation/structure/toxins.

Stage-enriched chemistry.

— Mycelium (A): Defensive alkaloids (e.g., camptothecin, naltrindole, trigonelline), antioxidants (glutathione), primary energy routes (glycolysis/TCA) and lipid signals (prostaglandin E_2 , jasmonates) dominated, reflecting substrate colonization and stress adaptation (Fernie et al., 2004; Beccaccioli & Marzia, 2019; Wang et al., 2023).

— Fruiting body (B): Flavonoids/phenolics (genistein, dihydrokaempferol, syringic acid), structural glycans (xylobiose; N-acetylneuraminic acid), nucleosides (inosine/IMP; RNA turnover) and polyketide-linked toxicants (aflatoxin-related/MelQx-like) prevailed, consistent with pigmentation, spore protection, and ecological defense (Fesel & Zuccaro, 2016; Harborne, 2014; Dixon & CLS, 1999; Rushing & Selim, 2019; Choi et al., 2025).

Pathways (KEGG/GSEA). Fruiting bodies enriched phenylpropanoid/flavonoid/isoflavonoid and tryptophan/tyrosine metabolism; mycelia enriched glycolysis/TCA, fatty-acid, and nucleotide biosynthesis. Broad secondary-metabolite pathways (ko01110) spanned both but were stronger in fruiting bodies; aflatoxin/polyketide signatures tracked the toxicant profile in Group B.

Biological significance. The data support developmental reprogramming from a growth/defense vegetative stage to a reproduction/pigment/defense fruiting stage, a pattern well recognized in basidiomycetes (Moore et al., 2020; Beccaccioli & Marzia, 2019).

Detection of potential drug leads (camptothecin, lycorine; antioxidants) underscores bioprospecting value (Wink, 2015; Wang et al., 2023), while aflatoxin-related chemistry flags a safety imperative for downstream processing (Rushing & Selim, 2019; Choi et al., 2025).

Conclusion

We document the first verified record of *Inonotus hispidus* in Mongolia and delineate developmental metabolomic reprogramming between mycelium and fruiting bodies. Fruitings emphasize phenylpropanoid/flavonoid and polyketide defense/pigment routes; mycelia emphasize energy generation, antioxidants, and defensive alkaloids. These findings support targeted bioprospecting while underscoring the need to mitigate aflatoxin-related risks during processing.

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Importance and Cultivation of Medicinal Mushrooms in India

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Abstract

Medicinal mushrooms have gained considerable attention worldwide due to their therapeutic potential, nutritional value, and applications in functional foods and nutraceuticals. In India, mushrooms have been traditionally used in folk medicine by various tribal and rural communities for the treatment of different ailments. Ethnomycological studies indicate that nearly 100 species of macrofungi belonging to about 56 genera are used by indigenous communities in different regions of India for medicinal purposes, highlighting their cultural and therapeutic importance.

Medicinal mushrooms contain a wide range of bioactive compounds such as polysaccharides (especially β -glucans), triterpenoids, phenolic compounds, sterols, proteins, and vitamins, which exhibit antioxidant, antitumor, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory and antidiabetic properties, making mushrooms valuable resources for pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries. India possesses favorable agro-climatic conditions and abundant agricultural residues, which support large-scale mushroom cultivation.

Species such as oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus* spp.), milky mushroom (*Calocybe indica*), button mushroom (*Agaricus bisporus*) and medicinal species like *Ganoderma lucidum*, *Lentinus edodes* are widely cultivated due to their adaptability and economic value. Cultivation of these mushrooms also contributes to waste recycling, rural employment and nutritional security, as mushrooms are rich in proteins, dietary fiber, essential amino acids, vitamins and minerals while being low in fat. Thus, medicinal mushrooms represent an important component of sustainable agriculture and healthcare in India.

Their cultivation not only provides nutritional and economic benefits but also supports the development of natural therapeutics and value-added products, emphasizing the need for further research, conservation and commercialization of indigenous medicinal mushroom resources.

Keywords: *Ganoderma lucidum*, nutritional value, *Agaricus bisporus*, antioxidant, antimicrobial

Utilization of mushroom waste for biopolymer production

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Abstract

The rapid increase in solid waste generated by industrial activities presents significant environmental challenges. In particular, the processing of mushrooms, especially species of the genus *Pleurotus*, generates considerable by-products that are often underutilized. These wastes, however, are rich in bioactive polysaccharides such as β -glucan and chitin, which exhibit unique physicochemical properties, biodegradability, and biocompatibility, making them attractive for various biopolymer applications. In this study, optimal conditions for extracting β -glucan and chitin from mushroom waste using conventional methods were determined. Water-soluble β -glucan was obtained at a yield of 5.23%, and chitin was recovered at a yield of 22.3%. The crude extracts were purified via reprecipitation, and their structural and thermal properties were characterized using FT-IR spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The results demonstrate that mushroom-processing waste can serve as a sustainable source of high-value biopolymers. Utilizing these by-products not only adds economic value but also contributes to environmental sustainability by promoting waste valorization. These findings highlight the potential of integrating mushroom waste-derived biopolymers into industrial and biomedical applications, offering a promising approach to resource-efficient and eco-friendly material production.

Keywords: *Pleurotus ostreatus*, β -glucan, chitin, chitosan, waste valorization, biopolymers

Introduction

Mushroom cultivation and processing generate substantial waste, including non-edible stems, broken or misshapen fruiting bodies, and mechanically contaminated materials (Wu et al., 2004; Munkhgerel et al., 2024). Although often discarded, these residues are rich in valuable biopolymers such as β -glucan, chitin, and chitosan, which possess biodegradability, biocompatibility, and potential therapeutic properties (Zannat et al., 2025). The effective utilization of these wastes provides a sustainable approach for producing high-value biopolymers while simultaneously reducing environmental impact (Smith. P. J., et al., 2024).

β -glucans, chitin, and chitosan are widely used in food, pharmaceutical, agricultural, and environmental applications. Extraction and purification of these biopolymers commonly employ water or alkaline treatments, followed by characterization using techniques such as FT-IR spectroscopy and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) to confirm their structural integrity and bioactivity (Thikham et al., 2023). However, optimized conditions for the sequential recovery of β -glucan and chitin from mushroom-processing waste remain limited, restricting efficient and scalable production. Therefore, this study aims to extract and characterize these biopolymers from mushroom residues and to determine optimal extraction conditions, thereby providing a sustainable strategy for waste valorization and high-value biopolymer production.

Materials and Methods

Mushroom-processing waste, including hard stems, broken or fragmented fruiting bodies, misshapen mushrooms, and materials contaminated with mechanical impurities, was collected during industrial oyster mushroom (*Pleurotus* spp.) cultivation. The samples were air-dried at room temperature (approximately 25°C) until a constant weight was achieved and then ground to a particle size of 2–3 mm. The milled material was stored in sealed plastic bags under ambient conditions prior to analysis.

All chemicals used in the experiments, including sodium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid, acetic acid, and ethanol, were of analytical grade. Distilled water was used for the preparation of all solutions.

Extraction and Purification of Biopolymers:

β -glucan and chitin were sequentially extracted from the prepared mushroom waste using alkali/acid treatments. Water soluble β -glucan was extracted under the optimal conditions: ratio of 1:10 (w/V) at 80°C for 2 h with constant stirring. To optimize extraction of chitin was using the Central Composite Design (CCD) in Design Expert 13 software (Munkhgerel et al., 2024).

Results and Discussion

The structural and physicochemical properties of the isolated biopolymers were confirmed using several analytical techniques. FT-IR spectroscopy was employed to identify the characteristic functional groups of β -glucan and chitin. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis was used to determine the crystallinity of the extracted chitin. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed to evaluate the thermal stability of the samples. Elemental analysis was conducted to verify the carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen composition of the isolated materials.

Water soluble β -glucan was successfully extracted from mushroom-processing waste under the optimal conditions (1:10 (w/V), 80°C, 2 h), with a yield of 5.23%. Subsequently, chitin was isolated from the remaining biomass (1:35 (w/V), 100°C, 3 h) with a significantly higher yield of 22.3%. These yields demonstrate the considerable potential of mushroom waste as a source for these high-value biopolymers.

The structural identity of the extracted β -glucan was confirmed by FT-IR analysis (Figure 1).

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of glucans

Figure 2. FT-IR spectra of chitins

The spectrum displayed characteristic absorption bands at 1029 and 1044 cm^{-1} , corresponding to β -glycosidic linkages. An absorption band at 870–895 cm^{-1} confirmed the β -configuration of the glycosidic bonds, while a minor signal in the 760–840 cm^{-1} range indicated the presence of α -linkages (Munkhgerel et al., 2024). These results demonstrate that non-edible mushroom residues are a viable source of structurally characterized, bioactive β -glucan.

Figure 3. TGA of chitins

FT-IR analysis of the extracted chitin (Figure 2) revealed the characteristic amide bands: amide I at approximately 1642 cm^{-1} , amide II at 1556 cm^{-1} , and amide III at 1369 cm^{-1} , confirming its polymeric structure. The thermal stability of the extracted chitin was evaluated by TGA (Figure 3), which showed a typical degradation profile for high-purity chitin. Furthermore, XRD analysis indicated a semi-crystalline structure, and elemental analysis confirmed the expected carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen composition.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that mushroom-processing waste is a sustainable and reliable source of high-value biopolymers. Under optimal conditions, water-soluble β -glucan and chitin were successfully extracted with yields of 5.23% and 22.3%, respectively. Comprehensive physicochemical characterization using FT-IR, XRD, TGA, and elemental analysis confirmed the structural integrity of both biopolymers, with chitin exhibiting a semi-crystalline structure, thermal stability, and the expected elemental composition. The extraction methods established in this work provide a critical foundation for scaling up production processes, thereby supporting the development of high-value applications for β -glucan and chitin in the food, pharmaceutical, and environmental industries. This approach contributes significantly to the valorization of industrial mushroom residues within a circular economy framework.

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Phytochemical assessment of some Nigerian *Ganoderma* species from different agro-ecological zones.

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Abstract

The *Ganoderma* genus is known possess curative abilities that can address a broad range of human illnesses. However, some Nigerian *Ganoderma* species could have needed phytochemical constituents that can compete with Lingzhi, Reishi or *G. lucidum*. This study seeks to examine the presence and quantitative phytochemicals on some Nigerian *Ganoderma* species collected from five ecological zones in Nigeria.

The outcome of this study showed the presence of saponin, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, tannin, coumarin, steroids, terpenoids, triterpenes and anthraquinone for ten *Ganoderma* species. Saponin levels ranged from 1.20% in *G. calidophilum* to 2.80% in *G. resinaceum*, with *G. lucidum* ($2.71 \pm 0.08\%$) and *G. resinaceum* ($2.80 \pm 0.12\%$). Alkaloid percentages were highest in *G. lucidum* ($4.82 \pm 0.04\%$) and *G. resinaceum* ($4.69 \pm 0.05\%$).

Flavonoid concentrations were highest in *G. sinensis* (3.44 ± 0.11 mg/g QE), followed by *G. austral* (3.09 mg/g QE) and *G. leucocontextum* (2.92 ± 0.33 mg/g QE). Phenolic compounds were abundant in *G. resinaceum* (1.82 ± 0.07 mg/g GAE), *G. sinensis* (1.57 ± 0.09 mg/g), and *G. applanatum* (1.41 ± 0.08 mg/g). Tannin levels were highest in

G. applanatum (1.23 ± 0.06 mg/g G AE) and *G. leucocontextum* (1.07 ± 0.04 mg/g), and the lowest in *G. lucidum* (0.06 mg/g). There were significant differences ($P < 0.01$) across all phytochemical parameters among the *Ganoderma* species. *Ganoderma resinaceum*, *G. sinensis*, and *G. applanatum* emerged as the most promising candidates for pharmaceutical exploration, particularly for their elevated levels of alkaloids, flavonoids, and tannins. This study further observed more *Ganoderma resinaceum* abundance from sahel savannah while derived and tropical rainforest zone remains the zones to beat for *Ganoderma* diversity and rich bioactive compounds in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Ganoderma*, phytochemical, quantitative, ecological, species.

Research Progress on the Resource Utilization of Spent Mushroom Substrate

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Abstract

With the rapid development of China's the edible mushroom industry, the output of spent mushroom substrate (SMS) has been increasing year by year, exceeding 130 million tons in 2024. This article systematically reviews recent research progress on the resource utilization of SMS in the fields of soil improvement, agricultural fertilizers, secondary mushroom cultivation, animal feed, and bioenergy. The main pathways for its recycling are discussed, aiming to provide a reference for in-depth research on high-value utilization technologies of SMS and the sustainable development of the edible mushroom industry.

Keywords: Soil Conditioner; Agricultural Fertilizer; Secondary Mushroom Cultivation; Animal Feed; Production of Bioenergy

Introduction

The edible mushroom industry is the fifth-largest planting industry in China, following grains, vegetables, fruits, and oilseeds. In 2020, the national total output of edible mushrooms exceeded 40 million tons, with an output value surpassing 300 billion RMB 1. By 2024, the national total output reached 43.9064 million tons, with a total output value of 417.64 billion RMB, accounting for over 85% of the global total production 1-2. The amount of SMS generated is 3 to 5 times that of mushroom yield³. In 2024, the edible mushroom industry

produced over 130 million tons of SMS. If not properly managed, these residues not only represent a waste of resources but also pose environmental pollution problems⁴. Therefore, scientifically sound and high-value conversion of waste SMS into valuable resources, achieving its reuse, has become an urgent problem for the edible mushroom industry. This paper summarizes the current status of the comprehensive utilization of SMS, providing new ideas for its resource recycling.

Composition of Spent Mushroom Substrate

Spent mushroom substrate refers to the waste substrate remaining after mushroom harvest, which has been colonized and partially degraded by fungal mycelia. It is also known as mushroom waste, mushroom residue, waste fungal logs, or spent mushroom compost. Its composition is significantly influenced by the cultivated mushroom species and the formulation of the growth medium. It typically contains residues of raw materials such as sawdust, straw, cottonseed hull, corncob, and wheat bran, primarily composed of residual fungal mycelia and incompletely degraded cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Simultaneously, SMS is rich in organic matter and mineral nutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. It contains relatively high levels of crude protein, crude fiber, amino acids, polysaccharides, as well as nitrates and phosphates, accompanied by various bioactive components, including enzymes and vitamins⁴⁹.

Furthermore, secondary metabolites with antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory functions have been detected in some SMS, further expanding its application potential in fields such as agriculture, feed, and biomedicine¹⁰. Modification treatments of SMS through physical, chemical, or biological methods can effectively enhance its added value, enabling efficient resource recycling. The resource utilization of SMS is not only an inevitable choice for waste management but also a crucial pathway for promoting sustainable agricultural development, reducing environmental pollution, and building a resource-conserving society.

Current Research Status of Spent Mushroom Substrate Applications

Research on the development and utilization of spent mushroom substrate began in China as early as the 1980s. Initial studies primarily focused on the secondary use of SMS in agricultural fertilizers and soil conditioners, animal feed, edible mushroom cultivation substrates, and biogas production. In recent years, with growing environmental awareness and the progressive maturation of technologies such as pyrolysis carbonization, anaerobic digestion, and densification molding in China, the value of SMS has become evident not only in agriculture and animal husbandry but also in the food and industrial sectors. Applications now include the production of high-value-added products, bioenergy, and environmental remediation materials.

Spent Mushroom Substrate as a Soil Conditioner and Agricultural Fertilizer

Spent mushroom substrate has a loose structure and is rich in various nutrients, including organic matter, nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium. It can serve as an effective organic fertilizer or soil conditioner when applied to farmland, improving soil compaction, enhancing soil fertility, and increasing crop yields 11-13. Currently, substrates for vegetable and fruit seedlings primarily rely on non-renewable resources such as peat, perlite, and vermiculite, which are costly and impact ecological balance¹². Tang et al. ¹¹ found that applying SMS from *Pleurotus ostreatus*, *Flammulina filiformis*, or *Auricularia heimuer* as organic fertilizer in paddy fields significantly improved crop yield and soil nutrient content. Ma et al. ¹⁴ reported that mulching with *Pholiota nameko* SMS in a hazelnut orchard increased soil fertility, suppressed weed species, and enhanced leaf quality and nut characteristics. Zhou et al. ¹⁵ discovered that applying SMS organic fertilizer at rates of 0.25%–1.5% to spinach could increase spinach yield and soil nutrients.

Spent Mushroom Substrate for Secondary Mushroom Cultivation

As the residual substrate after mushroom harvesting, spent mushroom substrate still contains a certain amount of incompletely degraded lignocellulosic materials, residual mycelia, and fungal metabolites. These components endow it with the potential to serve as a cultivation substrate for subsequent cycles of mushroom and horticultural crop production¹⁶⁻¹⁷. For instance, SMS can be mixed in different proportions with fresh cultivation materials (such as straw, sawdust) to formulate new growth media¹⁸. This approach not only effectively reduces the cost of new substrates but also reutilizes the residual nutrients in SMS, thereby decreasing the amount of waste generated¹⁶.

Application of Spent Mushroom Substrate in Animal Feed

The application of spent mushroom substrate in animal feed represents a significant pathway for its comprehensive utilization, embodying the concept of a circular economy and converting waste into valuable feed resources. Bioactive compounds present in SMS, such as phenolics, polysaccharides, saponins, and sterols, possess antioxidant and immunomodulatory functions. Incorporating SMS into feed can enhance animal performance [11]. Long et al. ¹⁹ demonstrated that a fermented total mixed ration containing 30% *Flammulina velutipes* SMS could improve rumen fermentation and rumen microbial composition in Guizhou black goats, thereby enhancing growth performance, apparent digestibility, and immunity. Liu et al. ²⁰ added fermented *Pleurotus eryngii* SMS to beef cattle diets, replacing part of the concentrated supplement. The results showed that replacing part of the concentrate with fermented *P. eryngii* SMS had no significant effect on the growth performance of beef cattle but significantly increased the apparent digestibility of crude protein, neutral detergent fiber, and acid detergent fiber in the diet.

Production of Bioenergy from Spent Mushroom Substrate

Converting waste SMS into bioenergy not only effectively addresses the challenge of agricultural solid waste management but

also extends the industrial chain and enhances added value, creating new economic growth points and providing sustained momentum for the green transformation of agriculture 21. Through technical means such as densification, anaerobic digestion, and pyrolysis, SMS can be processed into biomass pellets, biogas, ethanol, and biochar. As a fuel, it possesses high combustion efficiency, can effectively reduce waste emissions, thereby mitigating environmental pollution, and facilitates the resource utilization and harmless treatment of waste. Moreira et al.²² processed *Pleurotus ostreatus* SMS by drying, grinding, and compressing it into combustion-grade biosolids of medium quality. Rao et al.²³ concluded through experiments that the best compression molding effect for *Flammulina velutipes* SMS was achieved at a moisture content of 11%–14%, temperature of 100–120°C, pressure of 3–5 kN, and particle size of 0–5 mm.

Existing Problems

The broad prospects of spent mushroom substrate in agricultural and energy applications are constrained by its inherent characteristics and processing technologies. Current problems mainly include the following aspects: The chemical composition and nutrient distribution of SMS are often imbalanced, making it difficult to precisely match the requirements of target crops or fungal species, especially in secondary cultivation and fertilizer applications. Long-term safety assessments of risks associated with residual heavy metals and harmful substances in soil improvement and animal feed applications are insufficient. Accumulation of high salt content may lead to soil salinization and inhibition of plant growth.

The widespread presence of pathogens and anti-nutritional factors poses potential threats to animals and the environment. Furthermore, the heterogeneity of its physical properties and high cellulose content can reduce energy conversion efficiency or affect microbial decomposition. In large-scale applications, economic costs and the complexity of treatment processes further limit its utilization efficiency, and concerns regarding potential impacts on ecological sustainability require continued attention.

Prospects

Future research should focus on the development of efficient, sustainable technologies and the optimization of comprehensive utilization models. Regarding pretreatment technologies, innovative processes such as directed enzymatic hydrolysis, biochar production, and microbial enhancement should be introduced to improve the efficiency of SMS resource utilization. To address heavy metal and salt residue issues, techniques like nanomaterial adsorption or microbial regulation could be employed for efficient pollutant passivation and removal. Further exploration is needed into the synergistic high-value utilization of SMS with other agricultural wastes, such as co-composting, complementary energy conversion, or the development of refined feeds.

The application of metagenomics and metabolomics technologies should be fully leveraged to optimize the dynamic matching mechanisms between microorganisms and nutrients, thereby enhancing agricultural value and ecological carrying capacity. Additionally, practical research based on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) will provide a scientific basis for policy formulation and industrial adoption, ultimately promoting the efficient and green circular utilization of spent mushroom substrate.

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Session II. OTHER ORGANISMS' WHIT IN THE FUNGAL KINGDOM**Biotechnological potential of endophytic micro fungi of the genus *Alternaria* isolated from the Desert-steppe plants of Mongolia**

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Abstract

A total of 14 endophytic fungi isolated from eight desert-steppe plants of Mongolia and assigned to the genus *Alternaria* by their morphology and sequences of the rDNA internal transcribed spacer (ITS) regions were studied for antimicrobial activity and production of extracellular enzymes of medicinal, food and agricultural importance. Results received showed that only three strains, among them two strains that closely related to *Alternaria radicina*, had antimicrobial activity. As for extracellular enzymes, 92.9% produced amylase and fibrinolytic proteases, 85.7% produced cellulase, and all 14 strains studied produced L-asparaginase. Thus, the endophytic microfungi studied had a high biotechnological potential for production of extracellular enzymes.

Key words. L-asparaginase, cellulase, fibrinolytic activity, agriculture, arid area

Introduction

Endophytic microfungi have been recognized as a valuable but little explored source for screening of bio-active compounds important for the development of biotechnology (Tan & Zhou, 2001; Tiwari & Bae, 2022). It was shown that they could be more prolific producers than the soil fungi. Schultz et al. (2002) found out that among 135 isolated metabolites the proportion of novel structures produced by endophytes (51%) was considerably higher than that produced by soil isolates (38%).

Study on endophytic fungi of Mongolian plants revealed that they could be a promising source for screening of bio-active compounds (Enkh-Amgalan, 2013; Tsetseg et al., 2013; Adiyadolgor & Enkh-Amgalan, 2014). The more so as there are 3041 species of plants in Mongolia [Shuherdorj et al, 2022] rich in medicinal and endemic species, and just a small part of them has been studied for endophytes so far. In this paper we present the results of evaluation of 14 strains of the genus *Alternaria* isolated from eight Mongolian desert-steppe plants for production of amylase and cellulose important for food and agricultural biotechnologies and fibrinolytic proteases and L-asparaginase important for medical biotechnology as well as their antimicrobial activities. Microscopic fungi of the genus *Alternaria* of the family Pleosporaceae are the widely distributed fungi in the world. At present the genus consists of 792 registered species, which are grouped into 29 sections (Vinogradova et al., 2026; Woudenberg et al., 2013). In Mongolia It has been registered as one of the dominant genera of soil fungi (Tsetseg et al., 2016).

Material and methods

In total 14 strains of endophytic microfungi assigned to the genus *Alternaria* by their morphology and phylogenetic analysis of the ITS region sequences were used in this study. Details of molecular identification will be given in the subsequent publication. Strains were isolated from upper parts of eight plants by the method of Igarashi et al. (2002) with slight modification. *Caragana microphylla* (Pall.) Lam. (strains MN12-FE1-2 and MN12-FE3-1), *Cynomorium songaricum*

Rupr. (strain MN12-FE35), *Haloxylon ammodendron* (C.A.Mey.) Bge. (strains MN12-FE10 and MN12-FE11), *Reaumuria soongorica* (Pall.) Maxim. (strain MN12-FE25) and *Salsola passerina* Bge. (strains MN12-FE17 and MN12-FE18-1) were collected on the territory of South-Gobi aimag and *Allium anisopodium* L. (strains MN12-FE6, MN12-FE7 and MN12-FE9), *Sanguisorba officinalis* L. (strain MN12-FE20) and *Vincetoxicum sibiricum* (L.) Decne. (strains MN12-FE12 and MN12-FE14) - on the territory of Zavkhan aimag.

The microfungi strains grown on the potato-dextrose agar (PDA) for 5-7 days were used for evaluation of their biotechnological potential. Antimicrobial activities were tested against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* by the agar-diffusion method (Egorov, 1965). Potential for amylase production was tested on agar plates supplemented with 1% of starch and flooded with Lugol's iodine solution. Activity for L-asparaginase production was identified by a rapid plate assay method described by Gulati et al. (1997). Potential for cellulase production was identified after 3 days on agar plates supplemented with 0.5% Na-carboxymethyl cellulose after flooding them with 0.1% Congo red (Carder, 1986). Fibrinolytic activity was estimated by measuring the diameter of a clear zone formed on plasminogen-free fibrin plates after incubation at 37°C for 3, 6, 12 and 24 hours (Astrup & Mullertz, 1952).

Results and discussion

Molecular identification revealed that 13 strains of endophytic microfungi isolated from eight desert-steppe plants belonged to the genus *Alternaria*. Ten of them were the closest to species *Alternaria tenuissima* of the section *Alternaria* and three of them - to *Alternaria radicina* of the section *Radicina*. The 14th strain (MN12-FE9) taken for study was assigned to the genus *Alternaria* based on microscopic observations.

Antimicrobial activity

All 10 strains that closely related to *A. tenuissima* had no antimicrobial activities against test-microbes used. However, two out of three strains closely relating to *A. radicina* showed antimicrobial activities: one of them against four test-microbes and another one against all test-microbes used including *A. niger* (Table 1). As for *Alternaria sp.*, it was active against four test-microbes.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of endophytic fungi isolated from the desert-steppe plants
(diameter of zones, mm)

Plant name and aimag	Strain ID	Closest species	Plant part	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	<i>A. niger</i>
<i>Haloxylon ammodendron</i> (C.A.Mey.) Bge., South Gobi	MN12-FE10	<i>Alternaria radicina</i>	Leaf	13.5	15.5	13	9.5	0
<i>Cynomorium songaricum</i> Rupr., South Gobi	MN12-FE35	<i>Alternaria radicina</i>	Seed	13.5	12	13	10	9
<i>Allium anisopodium</i> L., Zavkhan	MN12-FE9*	<i>Alternaria</i> sp.	Flower	9.5	12	10.5	9	0

* assigned to the genus *Alternaria* by morphology

Production of extracellular enzymes

Most isolates of the endophytic microfungi of the genus *Alternaria* had a potential for production of all four enzymes studied: 92.9% produced amylase and fibrinolytic proteases, 85.7% produced cellulase, and all 14 strains studied produced L-asparaginase (Table 2, Fig. 1). Among them strain MN12-FE11 had no amylolytic and cellulolytic activities, strain MN12-FE12 had no cellulolytic activity and strain MN12-FE14 did not show fibrinolytic activity.

As for fibrinolytic activities of other strains, there were no strains with fibrinolytic activity after 3 hours of observation. After 6 hours strains MN12-FE6 and MN12-FE9 showed small activities and after 24 hours 13 strains produced the enzyme (Fig. 1). It is necessary to note that sizes of activity and a number of active strains increased with the time of observation.

Table 2. Number of strains of the genus *Alternaria* producing extracellular enzymes

Total strains studied	Closest species	Amylase	Cellulase	L-Asparaginase	
				24 h	48 h
10	<i>Alternaria tenuissima</i>	9	8	9	10
3	<i>Alternaria radicina</i>	3	3	3	3
1	<i>Alternaria</i> sp.*	1	1	1	1

The highest amylolytic activity showed strain MN12-FE14 (*V. sibiricum*, Zavkhan), and the highest cellulolytic activity – strains MN12-FE6 (*A. anizopodium*, Zavkhan) and MN12-FE10 (*Haloxylon ammodendron*, South Gobi).

Fig 1. Fibrinolytic activity of endophytic fungi of the genus *Alternaria*

As for important for the medicine enzymes, the highest L-asparaginase activity had strains MN12-FE1-2 (*C. microphylla*, South Gobi), and MN12-FE6 (*A. anizopodium*, Zavkhan) and the highest fibrinolytic activity - strains MN12-FE1-2 (*C. microphylla*, South Gobi), MN12-FE7 (*A. anizopodium*, Zavkhan) and MN12-FE12 (*V. sibiricum*, Zavkhan). Most strains with the highest activities were closest to *A. tenuissima* besides of strain MN12-FE10 that was the closest to *A. radicina*.

Conclusion

Results received indicate that the endophytic microfungi of the genus *Alternaria* isolated from the desert-steppe plants of Mongolia had a high potential for production of extracellular enzymes of medicinal, food and agricultural importance. So, they are of interest for further investigation in the liquid fermentation.

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Research Results on Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi from Khentii Province, Mongolia

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Abstract

Research on the diversity of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and their ecological significance in Mongolia has been conducted since 2010. The level of root mycorrhizal colonization ranged from 0.0% to 42.5%, while spore density in the soil varied between 25 and 215 spores per 100 g of soil. The average mycorrhizal colonization across all samples was 12.84%, and the mean spore density was 100.59 spores per 100 g of soil.

Keywords: Arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi, spor density, mycorrhizal colonization

Introduction

Khentii Province belongs to the Khentii physical-geographical region according to the classification of Sh. Tsegmid (1969). Mongolia is divided into 16 phytogeographical regions based on vegetation-geographical zoning, as proposed by N. Ulziikhutag (1989). Within this framework, the territory of Khentii Province falls into three phytogeographical regions. According to the phytogeographical classification of Mongolia by A. A. Yunatov (1950), the flora of Mongolia comprises 3,191 species of vascular plants belonging to 684 genera and 108 families (Uurgamal ba busad, 2019). At the scale of Khentii Province, a total of 1,236 species of vascular plants have been recorded (Sukherdorj Baasanmunkh et al., 2022). Research on the diversity of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF) and their ecological

significance in Mongolia has been conducted since 2010. Studies of steppe ecosystems have shown that the genus *Glomus* is dominant, with *Glomus intraradices* and *Glomus irregulare* identified as the dominant species (Goomaral et al., 2012). In addition, AMF investigations have been carried out in various plant communities in the Shajin Khurkh valley of Bogd Khan Mountain (Densmaa et al., 2013).

Furthermore, experimental studies have examined the role of *Diversispora spurca* in improving drought tolerance of *Stipa krylovii* (feather grass) growing in the vicinity of Ulaanbaatar, particularly through its presence in seeds, roots, and soil (Burenjargal et al., 2013). There are also studies demonstrating the use of mycorrhiza in the restoration of degraded lands in Iceland, where tree and perennial plant establishment was enhanced (Enkhtuya B., 2003).

Moreover, a doctoral study entitled “Endomycorrhizal structure and diversity of arbuscular mycorrhiza associated with common plants in diverse plant communities of Tuv Province” identified endomycorrhizal colonization levels in 69 plant species and recorded 34 endomycorrhizal species belonging to 10 genera and 6 families. Among these, *Acaulospora* and *Glomus* were the dominant genera, while *Claroideoglomus etunicatum* was identified as a dominant species (Munkhzul Ts. 2018, 2023).

Materials and methods

A total of 450 soil samples were collected from 50 sites (with 9 replicates per site) across the forest-steppe and steppe zones of Khentii Province. The nine replicate samples from each site were composited, resulting in 50 samples. These samples were used to assess the level of arbuscular mycorrhizal (AM) colonization and to identify AM fungi to the genus level based on morphological characteristics. The level of mycorrhizal colonization was determined using 10% KOH, a thermostatic chamber, 2% HCl, and trypan blue staining solution (Vierheilig et al., 1998). The stained plant roots were mounted on microscope slides using PVLG solution, covered with a coverslip, and observed under a light microscope to examine the

morphological structures of mycorrhiza (McGonigle et al., 1990). The percentage of mycorrhizal colonization was calculated following the method of Phillips & Hayman (1970). For the identification of AM fungal spores from soil, a centrifugation and sedimentation technique using 50–70% sucrose solution was applied to extract spores from soil samples (Gerdemann et al., 1963).

Spore identification was carried out using the taxonomic keys provided in the manual by Schenck and Perez, as well as the International Culture Collection of (Vesicular) Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi database INVAM (<https://invam.wvu.edu/>).

Results and Discussion

The results revealed that root mycorrhizal colonization ranged from 0.0% to 42.5%, while soil spore density varied from 25 to 215 spores per 100 g of soil. The overall mean colonization rate was 12.84%, and the average spore density was 100.59 spores per 100 g of soil. The highest colonization was recorded in sample MN257A, collected from the edge of a larch forest with dark chestnut soil and a plant community consisting of *Dasiphora fruticosa*, *Leymus chinensis*, *Stellera chamaejasme*, *Bupleurum scorzonerifolium*, and *Larix sibirica*.

By contrast, the highest spore density was found in sample MN2519A, collected from dark chestnut soil in a river meadow dominated by *Potentilla anserina*, *Carex duriuscula*, and *Leymus chinensis*, suggesting active distribution and reproductive activity of mycorrhizal fungi in this habitat. The variation in root colonization and spore density among samples indicates that AMF colonization and sporulation are strongly dependent on environmental conditions. High root colonization reflects active symbiotic association within the roots, whereas high spore density indicates strong reproductive capacity of the fungi in the soil.

Conclusion

In some samples, high spore density was observed despite low root colonization, suggesting that a direct linear relationship between spore accumulation and root colonization is not consistently present. This may be related to factors such as soil physicochemical properties, host plant characteristics, and the stage of active root growth. Therefore, in order to accurately evaluate the distribution and activity of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, both colonization and spore density should be investigated together and interpreted in relation to environmental conditions.

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Perspectives for the use of Myxomycetes as Bioindicators

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Abstract

Myxomycetes (Amoebozoa) are proposed as promising bioindicators, complementary to traditional spore-producing organisms such as lichens and mosses, long used for assessing air quality and environmental status. These amoeboid plasmodial protists are widespread in terrestrial ecosystems, occupy key positions in food webs, and display both broad and narrow ecological specialization across a wide range of plant-derived substrates. Their short life cycles, sensitivity to moisture, temperature, pH, light and pollution, and standardized detection via fruiting-body surveys and moist chamber cultures make them suitable for monitoring habitat quality, pollution impacts and effects of habitat fragmentation and land-use change. Practical applications have been demonstrated both in research and in educational projects with school and university students, confirming the feasibility of using myxomycetes as an informative and accessible bioindicator group.

Keywords: Amoebae, Amoebozoa, bioindication, protists, slime molds.

The use of spore-producing organisms (lichens, algae and mosses) to assess environmental quality has long been known and is widely applied in bioindication (Zechmeister et al., 2003; Nimis, Skert, 2006). Myxomycetes (Phylum Amoebozoa) can be regarded as promising bioindicators of terrestrial ecosystems because they

combine wide distribution, narrow ecological sensitivity, standardized methods of detection and recording, and relatively short life cycles.

Myxomycetes are amoeboid plasmodial protists that occur on a variety of plant-derived substrates, including living woody plants, decaying wood, forest litter and weathered dung of herbivorous animals. Both eurybiotic and stenobiotic species are found among myxomycetes. Their life cycle includes fruiting bodies, zoospores, myxamoebae and a multinucleate single-celled plasmodium. Zoospores, myxamoebae and plasmodia actively move in search of food and suitable sites for sporulation. The size of myxomycete fruiting bodies ranges from about 50 μm in *Echinostelium* species to up to 1 m in *Fuligo septica* (L.) F.H.Wigg. This group of protists forms an irreplaceable link in food webs: by feeding on fungal spores, algae, detritus and bacteria they regulate fungal and bacterial decomposition of organic matter in soil, leaf litter and decaying wood, while their plasmodia and fruiting bodies in turn represent an important food resource for various insect groups.

Myxomycetes are present in almost all terrestrial biomes and play a notable role within soil microbial communities, which makes them a convenient model group for assessing habitat quality. A key factor determining the suitability of myxomycetes for biomonitoring is their sensitivity to abiotic environmental parameters such as moisture, temperature, substrate acidity (pH), light regime and the level of anthropogenic pollution. Preliminary studies have shown that changes in bark and soil pH associated, for example, with acid precipitation and aerosol pollution are accompanied by shifts in species richness and community structure of corticolous myxomycetes, with reduced diversity observed near upper elevational limits of coniferous forests under increased atmospheric pollutant loads, suggesting that certain species and species assemblages may be considered candidates for a "biotic pollution index" (Baba, Sevindik, 2018).

Due to their short life cycles (from 3 days to 3 months in different species) and rapid responses to microclimatic changes, myxomycetes are also sensitive to climate variability and habitat fragmentation.

Studies in tropical and subtropical forests have demonstrated that conversion of forest stands into agricultural lands and pastures leads to changes in species composition and functional structure of myxomycete assemblages: the proportion of species associated with complex forest microhabitats decreases, whereas the proportion of eurytopic species characteristic of open habitats increases, and such shifts can serve as indicators of habitat loss and forest ecosystem degradation (Rojas, Doss, 2014).

Particular interest lies in using myxomycetes to assess the condition of woody vegetation. The species composition of myxomycetes on bark of living trees, mosses and lichens is sensitive to changes in moisture regime, aerosol pollution and stand structure. It has been shown that the richness of myxomycete species developing in moist chamber cultures on bark samples can be used for indirect assessment of tree “health” and the status of surrounding protected areas, as well as for comparing sites with different levels of anthropogenic impact (Keller, Everhart, 2010).

Finally, the versatility of myxomycetes as bioindicators is also linked to methodological advantages: their fruiting bodies are easily detected visually, they possess distinctive morphology, and their cultivation in moist chamber conditions allows standardized sampling and the acquisition of representative data on potential community composition under specified environmental parameters. Taken together, their sensitivity to physico-chemical environmental factors, rapid response to habitat disturbance, and accessibility for field and laboratory studies substantiate the use of myxomycetes as effective bioindicators of environmental quality and climate-driven changes across a wide range of terrestrial ecosystems.

The use of myxomycetes as bioindicators has been implemented by us both in research projects and in educational settings for creative projects by school pupils and in student research defenses. School projects have included, for example: “The influence of surface fire on the species composition of myxomycetes in a mixed forest near the Karakan River (Russia, Novosibirsk)”, “First data on myxomycete biodiversity in the ‘Legostaevsky’ reserve and its

surroundings”, “Use of fungus-like protists (class Myxomycetes) as bioindicators of environmental condition in the Sovetsky district of Novosibirsk”, and “The impact of road traffic on the species diversity of epiphytic myxomycetes inhabiting Scots pine”. Student projects have included, among others, “Life strategies of epiphytic myxomycetes in the Kirovsky district of Tomsk”.

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Characterization of functional traits of Ecto- and endophytic fungi strains isolated from Larch Forest trees in Mongolia.

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Abstract

Larix sibirica LEDEB (Siberian larch tree) is a dominant and ecologically important conifer species that forms large areas of boreal forests across Mongolia, Russia, and the northeastern regions of Asia. It plays an important ecological and economic role in boreal forest ecosystems through carbon sequestration, timber production, and soil stabilization. It demonstrates strong adaptation to severe environmental conditions, including extremely low temperatures, water limitation, and nutrient-poor soils.

Siberian larch tree is a deciduous conifer species that is obligately dependent on ectomycorrhizal (EM) and endophytic fungi for survival and growth, particularly in the harsh, nutrient-poor, and cold soils of the boreal forests of Mongolia. These fungi form a symbiotic relationship with the larch roots, improving water and nutrient uptake (specifically nitrogen and phosphorus) and boosting tolerance to environmental stress. This study aimed to isolate and identify functional traits of ectomycorrhizal and endophytic fungi strains associated with *Larix sibirica* Ledeb.

Several fungi synthesize IAA via tryptophan-dependent pathways, enhancing plant development and symbiosis. Phosphate-

solubilizing fungi (PSF) also improve plant nutrition by releasing organic acids that mobilize insoluble phosphate compounds, but plant growth-promoting activities in ectomycorrhizal and endophytic fungi strains associated with *Larix sibirica* Ledeb. are less investigated in Mongolia. Based on the morphological and molecular analyses of the rDNA internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region, a total of 12 ectomycorrhizal and 21 endophytic fungal culturable strains were isolated.

In Endophytic fungi isolates, *Penicillium* (7), *Fusarium* (4), *Diaporthe* (4), *Chaetomium* (3), *Stagonospora* (1), *Paraconiothyrium* (1), *Purpureocillium* (1), and in Ectomycorrhizal fungi *Sullius grevillei*, *Suillus clintonianus*, *Fungal sp*, *Lachnum sp*, *Phialocephala fortinii*, *Pseudogymnoascus sp*, *Thelebolales sp*, *Pseudogymnoascus roseus*, *Pezizomyces sp*, *Pleurotus oestreatus*, *Pholiota brunnescens* were identified. For Characterization of functional traits, among of isolated fungi, phosphate solubilization formed clear halos on Pikovskaya's medium in all endophytic strains and the highest phosphate solubilization index potential was in endophytic fungi in *Penicillium polonicum* (SI=2.29) and in ectomycorrhizal fungi, *Pseudogymnoascus sp* and *Fungal sp* (SI=2.26) and (SI=2.70), respectively, and are included in the considered moderate-growing group. IAA production activities in endophytic fungi strains range from 14,5 to 110 µg/mL, and the highest was in *Diaporthe eres* (110 µg/mL). In ectomycorrhizal fungi, the concentration of indole-3-acetic acid ranged from 1.1 to 9.9 µg/mL, with the highest value recorded in *Pezizomyces sp*. (9.9 µg/mL).

In summary, successfully isolated and identified pure fungal strains from Siberian Larch, many of which show potential to act as beneficial or mutualistic partners for host plants and can be used for plant growth, stress tolerance, and disease resistance.

Keywords: endophytic fungi, ectomycorrhizal fungi, phosphate solubilization, IAA,

Root Traits and Endophytic Fungal Associations in Wild Wheat Progenitor, *Aegilops tauschii* and Their Inheritance in Primary Synthetic Hexaploid Wheat Associated with Soil Environments

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Abstract:

Sustaining wheat productivity under climate change requires crop varieties with improved tolerance to environmental stresses and enhanced capacity to acquire water and nutrients under limiting conditions. The root system, often referred to as the “hidden half” of plants, plays a central role in these processes and in mediating interactions with soil microorganisms. However, modern wheat breeding has largely focused on aboveground traits, potentially narrowing genetic diversity for root-related characteristics and beneficial microbial associations. The wild progenitor *Aegilops tauschii*, the diploid D-genome donor of hexaploid wheat, represents an important genetic resource for restoring adaptive belowground traits. This study investigated how ploidy level, genomic composition, and soil-associated evolutionary environments influence root traits and fungal associations in wheat. Two greenhouse experiments were conducted using deep pots with low-nutrient sandy soil. The first compared diploid *Aegilops tauschii*, tetraploid *Triticum turgidum* cv. Langdon (LNG), and hexaploid *Triticum aestivum* cv. Norin 61 (N61). The second evaluated 36 primary synthetic (PS) wheat lines derived from d

iverse *Aegilops tauschii* accessions crossed with LNG and N61. Results showed that *Aegilops tauschii* exhibited superior root development and higher arbuscular mycorrhizal colonization while suppressing *Alternaria* infection compared with LNG and N61. These traits were partially inherited in PS lines, with variation linked to the soil origin of the accessions. Lines derived from Cambisols showed enhanced performance, whereas those from Gleysols and Calcisols exhibited weaker traits. These findings highlight the importance of integrating wild genetic resources with eco-edaphic context to develop wheat cultivars with improved root systems and greater resilience.

Keywords: Wheat ploidy, Genetic diversity; arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (AMF); *Serendipita indica*; *Alternaria*.

Introduction:

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) underpins global food security, yet climate change and fungal pathogens threaten significant yield losses (Savary et al. 2018; Li et al. 2021). Despite advances in breeding for aboveground traits, the root system—the “hidden half”—and its interactions with soil microbiomes remain underexplored (Bishopp and Lynch 2015; Ober et al. 2021). Root architecture governs water and nutrient acquisition and mediates associations with beneficial symbionts such as arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi, while also influencing susceptibility to pathogens like *Alternaria* spp. (Smith and Read 2010; Grebenikova et al. 2018). The wild progenitor *Aegilops tauschii*, donor of the D genome, represents a key resource for restoring adaptive root traits reduced during domestication (Marcussen et al. 2014; Wang et al. 2018). Synthetic hexaploid wheat offers potential to recover this diversity, yet trait inheritance and environmental effects remain unclear (Gaurav et al. 2022). This study evaluates root traits and fungal associations across ploidy levels.

Materials and methods:

Two greenhouse experiments were conducted at the Arid Land Research Center, Tottori University, using diploid *Aegilops tauschii*, tetraploid *Triticum turgidum* cv. Langdon (LNG), hexaploid *Triticum aestivum*

um cv. Norin 61 (N61), and 36 primary synthetic (PS) lines derived from crosses between LNG and diverse *A. tauschii* accessions. Plants were grown in tall pots (60 cm) filled with low-nutrient sandy soil collected from the same field. To simulate natural microbial conditions, a mixture of crude field fungal inoculum and a commercial arbuscular mycorrhizal fungus (*Rhizophagus irregularis*) was applied to the rhizosphere after germination. Experiments followed a randomized complete block design with six replicates under controlled greenhouse conditions without fertilizer input.

After 3–4 months, plants were harvested, and root systems were scanned to quantify architectural and morphological traits, while physiological traits were measured using elemental analysis. Root colonization by arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and other fungi was assessed using staining and the gridline intersect method. Statistical analyses included Welch's ANOVA, correlation analysis, and multivariate approaches (PCA and clustering) using SPSS and R.

Results:

In the first experiment, significant variation in root and biotic traits was observed across genotypes, while carbon, nitrogen, and C/N ratio remained unchanged. *Aegilops tauschii* consistently exhibited superior root architecture (length, surface area, volume, and biomass), followed by LNG and N61, with thin roots contributing most to resource acquisition. It also showed higher root tissue density and stronger colonization by (AMF), whereas N61 had higher dark DSE (*Alternaria*) colonization. AMF was positively correlated with root traits, while *Alternaria* showed negative associations. In the second experiment, most primary synthetic (PS) lines outperformed parental lines in root length and biomass. PS lines also exhibited higher colonization by AMF and *Serendipita indica* and generally lower *Alternaria* infection compared with N61. Root and shoot traits were positively correlated with beneficial fungi, while *Alternaria* showed negative relationships. Clustering and PCA grouped high-performing PS lines, particularly those derived from Cambisols, indicating strong soil-linked inheritance of root and microbial interaction traits.

Discussion:

In the first experiment, the superior root architecture of *Aegilops tauschii* confirms the critical role of the D genome in shaping belowground traits, particularly lateral root development (Wang et al. 2018). Its enhanced root system likely reflects adaptation to nutrient-limited environments, where efficient soil exploration is essential, unlike domesticated genotypes selected under high-input conditions (Wang et al. 2015). Root tissue density emerged as a more reliable adaptive trait than SRL, especially under stress. The strong association between root traits and AMF colonization, and the inverse relationship with DSE, highlights coordinated plant–microbe strategies. Variation among accessions suggests that both genetic background and native soil conditions shape root–fungal interactions, supporting the importance of eco-edaphic context in trait expression (Tkacz et al. 2020).

In the second experiment, substantial variation among PS lines demonstrates successful partial introgression of beneficial traits from *A. tauschii*. Enhanced root traits and increased AMF and *Serendipita indica* colonization, coupled with reduced *Alternaria*, confirm the value of the wild D genome. Positive associations between root traits and beneficial fungi emphasize functional integration, while negative correlations with *Alternaria* indicate improved resilience. Notably, superior PS lines were linked to Cambisol-derived progenitors, underscoring soil origin as a key determinant of trait expression. These findings highlight the combined influence of genetic introgression and soil adaptation in improving wheat performance.

Conclusion:

This study reveals substantial variation in root and biotic traits across *Aegilops tauschii*, cultivated wheat, and primary synthetic (PS) lines, which are the direct progeny of *A. tauschii*. The wild species exhibited superior root architecture, enhanced AMF colonization, and reduced DSE, confirming its value as a source of adaptive traits. These advantages were partially transferred to PS lines, with performance shaped by genomic background and soil origin, particularly Cambisols. Overall, integrating *A. tauschii* diversity and eco-edaphic context offers

a strong pathway for developing wheat with improved root systems and stress resilience.

limitations and Future directions:

Limitations include reliance on morphological fungal identification, single-environment conditions, limited *Aegilops tauschii* accessions, and use of only one tetraploid and one hexaploid check, with restricted PS diversity from a single AB background. Future work should integrate molecular tools, factorial designs, expanded germplasm (including MSDs), and genomic analyses, linking root traits to yield across diverse soils.

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Biodiversity of lichens in Mongolia and their adaptive characteristics

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate and explain the diversity of lichens in Mongolia and their adaptive characteristics. It synthesizes the ecological and biological foundations of lichen distribution patterns within the country's major vegetation zones, including high mountains, taiga forests, forest-steppe, dry steppe, desert steppe, and desert regions. The analysis is based on substrate and habitat-specific conditions that influence lichen adaptation.

Keywords: lichen diversity, mountain systems, diverse habitats,

Introduction

Due to Mongolia's vast territory and long-term environmental variability, a rich diversity of lichens has evolved, adapted to a wide range of surface, soil, and climatic conditions across all climatic zones.

The lichen flora of Mongolia includes two major groups—Ascolichens (Ascomycota) and Basidiolichens (Basidiomycota)—comprising 7 classes, 24 orders, 66 families, 215 genera, and 1,079 recorded species (Schubert & Klement, 1971; Tsogt, 1976; Golubkova, 1981; Byazrov, 1989; Cogt, 1995; Byazrov, 2006; Enkhtuya, 2007; Enkhtuya & Javkhlan, 2022).

Additionally, when including 103 species of non-lichenized saprotrophic and lichenicolous fungi, the total diversity reaches 1,182 species (Zhurbenko, Enkhtuya, Javkhlan, 2019; 2020).

The heterogeneous environments of Mongolia, particularly its mountainous regions, have resulted in highly diverse habitats. These conditions have led to the development of varied life forms and species compositions of lichens. Therefore, studying the ecological and biological basis of lichen adaptation, as well as their role within major climatic and geographical vegetation zones, is of significant scientific importance.

Methodology:

This study presents a general assessment of lichen diversity and adaptive patterns in Mongolia based on an integrated analysis of previously published literature and long-term original research data collected over several decades.

Data were compiled from taxonomic and ecological studies of lichen flora, with particular emphasis on species composition, distribution patterns, and ecological characteristics across major climatic and phytogeographical regions.

Results and Discussion:

The lichen flora of Mongolia exhibits distinct and unique characteristics. Mountainous regions, which cover approximately 42.09% of the country's territory, play a major role in determining lichen diversity. In particular, major mountain systems such as Khuvsgul, Khentii, Khangai, and the Mongolian Altai, along with their surrounding ranges, display well-developed altitudinal zonation. These areas provide a wide range of potential substrates, forming a highly diverse system for lichen development.

Due to the complex structure of mountainous terrain, lichen biota are distributed in a fragmented manner. The strong differentiation of relief has resulted in clear zonation patterns, which are fully reflected in the diversity of Mongolia's lichen flora. This study also explains the historical patterns of lichen formation in relation to vegetation zonation. The heterogeneous structure and composition of Mongolian lichen flora are interpreted through their origin and evolutionary development.

The lichen flora of Mongolia is considered to have formed over a long historical period at the intersection of the ancient Mediterranean and the Holarctic floristic regions. As a result, clear geographical differences are observed in species diversity and in the composition of families and genera. For example, the northern regions are characterized by Boreal elements of the Holarctic region, while the steppe regions are dominated by major Central Asian families (see Table 1). The lichen flora reflects florogenetic characteristics associated with three subregions and six provinces located at the boundary between the Eurasian and Irano-Turanian floristic regions.

Table 1. Distribution of Lichen Species Richness in Mongolia

Region	Sub Region	Phytogeographical Unit	District	Area, (%)	Number of species	Species Share, (%)	Species Recorded Only in This District	
Eurasian	Siberian Taiga	East Siberian Mountain Taiga	Khuvsgul	4.96	319	30.0	40	
			Khentii	3.05	407	37.7	49	
	Mongolian Mountain Forest-Steppe			Khangai	17.59	806	75.0	282
				Mongol-Daguur	6.62	100	9.27	2
		West Siberian Mountain Forest-Steppe		Khovd	1.98	204	18.9	19
				Mongolian Altai	7.02	316	29.3	38
		East Asian Mountain Forest-Steppe	Greater Khingan	0,87	56	5.2	0	
	Iran - Tu		Middle Khalkh (steppe)	11.54	171	15.8	3	

		Eastern Mongolia (steppe)	8.94	65	6.0	3	
		Great Lakes Depression (semi-desert steppe)	6.11	49	4.5	0	
Central Asian Steppe and Desert	Mongolian Steppe and Desert	Valley of Lakes (semi-desert steppe)	3.18	53	4.9	0	
		Eastern Gobi (semi-desert steppe)	9.35	39	3.6	0	
		Gobi Altai (semi-desert steppe)	5.02	107	9.91	10	
		Trans-Altai Gobi (desert)	5.72	38	3.52	0	
		Alashan Gobi (desert)	6.43	19	1.76	0	
		Kazakh Desert (Dzungarian-Turanian)	Dzungarian Gobi (desert)	1.62	34	3.15	1

Conclusion

The lichen flora of Mongolia has developed over a long historical period of increasing aridity. It consists of unique species that have adapted to continental climatic conditions, particularly in mountainous environments.

The findings suggest that:

- The climatic conditions of habitats determine the general structure of lichen flora.
- Substrate (субстрат) diversity directly influences species composition, richness, and adaptive capacity.

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Molecular Identification of *Trichoderma* spp. Isolated from Rhizospheric Soils in Mongolia

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Abstract

Species of the genus *Trichoderma* are widely distributed soil fungi commonly associated with plant roots, rhizosphere soils, and plant residues, and are extensively used as biological control agents against plant pathogens. In addition to their antagonistic potential, *Trichoderma* spp. function as plant growth-promoting fungi (PGPF), enhancing plant resistance to biotic and abiotic stresses and contributing to soil fertility through organic matter decomposition and nutrient cycling. The present study aimed to isolate and identify *Trichoderma* species from Rhizospheric soils collected in Ulaanbaatar city and Tov province, Mongolia, using morphological characteristics and ITS rDNA sequencing. Soil samples were processed using the dilution plate method on potato dextrose agar (PDA), resulting in the isolation of 15 fungal strains.

The isolates were initially characterized based on morphological features and subsequently subjected to molecular identification through PCR amplification of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region using ITS1 and ITS4 primers. Sequence analysis was performed using BLAST against the GenBank database. The results showed high similarity of the isolates with known *Trichoderma* species, including 98.49–100% similarity with *T. harzianum*, 97.7–99.5% with *T. citrinoviride*, and 96.78% with *T. virens*. Based on these findings, the isolates were identified as *T. harzianum*, *T. citrinoviride*, and *T. virens*. The study demonstrates that Rhizospheric soils in the selected regions harbor diverse *Trichoderma* species with potential applications in biological control. These findings provide a basis for further research

on the development of biofungicides for the management of soil-borne plant diseases.

Keywords: rhizosphere, ITS rDNA, fungal isolation, molecular identification, soil microbiota

Introduction and Research Problem

Species of *Trichoderma* are ubiquitous fungi found in soil and plant-associated environments, particularly in the rhizosphere. They are widely recognized for their role as biological control agents against plant pathogens and as plant growth-promoting fungi. Despite their importance, information on the diversity of *Trichoderma* spp. in Mongolian soils remains limited. Therefore, this study aimed to isolate and identify *Trichoderma* species from Rhizospheric soils using morphological and molecular approaches.

Materials and Methods

Soil samples were collected from multiple locations in Ulaanbaatar city and Tov province, Mongolia. The soil dilution plate method was used to isolate fungal strains on potato dextrose agar (PDA), followed by purification of cultures. A total of 15 isolates were obtained and characterized based on colony morphology and microscopic features. Molecular identification was carried out by PCR amplification of the internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region of rDNA using ITS1 and ITS4 primers. The obtained sequences were analyzed using BLAST in the GenBank database.

Results

The isolates were successfully obtained and identified using combined morphological and molecular analyses. BLAST results showed high similarity with known *Trichoderma* species: 98.49–100% with *T. harzianum*, 97.7–99.5% with *T. citrinoviride*, and 96.78% with *T. virens*. Based on sequence homology, isolates were identified as follows:

- *T. citrinoviride*: 16, 17, 22, 25

- *T. harzianum*: 5, 6, 9-1, 9-2, 9-2*, 18, 23, 24, 26
- *T. virens*: 21

Discussion and Conclusion

The study confirms that Rhizospheric soils in Ulaanbaatar and Tov province contain diverse *Trichoderma* species. The identified species are known for their ecological importance and potential application in biological control. These findings highlight the potential of native *Trichoderma* isolates as candidates for bio fungicide development. Further studies should focus on evaluating their antagonistic activity and effectiveness under greenhouse and field conditions.

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Morphological and trophic traits outweigh soil depth in shaping the climatic sensitivity of soil fungi in Mongolian arid grasslands

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Abstract

Soil fungi play essential roles in ecosystem functioning and are highly sensitive to environmental change. Understanding their biogeographic patterns across environmental gradients is therefore critical for predicting ecosystem responses to climate change. However, how climate influences fungal trophic groups across soil depths in arid ecosystems remains largely unknown. Here, we investigated how soil fungal community and its trophic trait groups vary with climate and soil depths (0–15 and 15–30 cm) in Mongolian arid grasslands. Our results show that fungal communities were dominated by stress-tolerant filamentous taxa, primarily belonging to a few classes of Ascomycota.

Mean annual precipitation (MAP) was the dominant driver of taxonomic turnover (Bray–Curti's dissimilarity) for total fungi and trophic groups at both soil depths. At the taxonomic level, climate effects on pathotroph and symbiotrophs decreased with soil depth. However, climate effects on phylogenetic turnover (β -mean pairwise distance) were weaker, with MAP influencing total fungal community only in the subsoil (15–30 cm). Among trophic groups, phylogenetic turnover responded differently: saprotrophs showed significant climatic responses across soil depths, whereas pathotrophs responded only in the topsoil.

Overall, climatic effects on fungal trophic groups were more pronounced than depth-related differences, highlighting the importance

of trait-based approaches for predicting belowground responses to climate change in arid grasslands.

Key words: climate sensitivity, taxonomic turnover, phylogenetic turnover, fungal assembly

Introduction

Fungi play a fundamental role in ecosystem functioning. However, knowledge of fungal diversity and distribution remains limited, despite fungi comprising approximately 20% of all eukaryotic species on Earth (Niskanen et al., 2023). Climate change and associated extreme events are expected to strongly influence fungal communities (Větrovský et al., 2019). Understanding how climate influences soil fungal distribution and abundance at regional and global scales is therefore critical, as fungi contribute to key ecosystem functions, including nutrient cycling, carbon sequestration, and organic matter decomposition (Maestre et al., 2025). At the global scale, climatic variables are the primary determinants of soil fungal richness and community composition, followed by edaphic and spatial factors (Tedersoo et al., 2014). Nevertheless, this knowledge remains scarce in Mongolian arid grasslands.

Materials and methods

In this study, we examined soil samples collected across climatic gradients in Mongolian arid grasslands, from two different soil depths: 0–15 cm and 15–30 cm. Soil properties were previously reported by Khishigmaa et al. (2024). Soil microbial genomic DNA was extracted using DNeasy PowerSoil Pro kit (QIAGEN). To identify soil fungal community, the ITS region was amplified using a barcoded primer set. The amplicons were sequenced on the Illumina Novoseq P6000 platform. To classify fungal taxa into different trophic and morphological trait groups, we used FungalTraits (Pölme et al., 2020). All statistical analyses were performed in R software.

Results and Discussion

The soil fungal community was dominated by *Eurotiomycetes*, *Sordariomycetes*, *Dothideomycetes*, and *Leotiomycetes*, with substantial variation in their relative abundances across soil depths (0–15 and 15–30 cm). This predominance of Ascomycota in Mongolian arid grasslands is consistent with findings from global soil studies (Egidi et al., 2019; Větrovský et al., 2019). Such dominance likely reflects their high genomic capacity for resource utilization, strong competitive ability, and tolerance to environmental stress (Egidi et al., 2019).

Partial Mantel tests identified mean annual precipitation (MAP) as the strongest driver of taxonomic turnover in fungal communities across soil depths. This supports the widely recognized importance of water availability in structuring fungal communities in arid ecosystems (Mikryukov et al., 2023). However, phylogenetic turnover (β -mean pairwise distance) of the overall fungal community was influenced by MAP only in the subsoil.

Depth-dependent climatic effects were more evident for specific trophic groups. At taxonomic level, pathotrophs and symbiotrophs showed stronger climate-driven responses in the topsoil. In contrast, at the phylogenetic level, climatic influences varied among trophic groups. Climatic effects on the phylogenetic turnover of saprotrophs were significant across both soil depths, whereas those on pathotrophs were significant only in the topsoil. Soil properties, in general, exerted a strong influence on the phylogenetic turnover of trophic groups, with pronounced effect of soil organic matter on symbiotrophs in both soil depths.

Conclusion

Our results demonstrate that changes in taxonomic composition of soil fungal communities, reflecting relatively recent responses, are primarily shaped by climatic factors. In contrast, phylogenetic turnover, which reflects longer-term environmental responses, appears to be more strongly governed by soil properties. Differences in the relative importance of climate and soil properties were particularly evident among trophic groups, highlighting the importance of considering functional guilds in understanding soil fungal ecology.

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Session III. POSTER PRESENTATIONS

The fatty acid profile of goat meat products fortified with mushrooms

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the chemical composition and fatty acid profile as well as the shelf life of the goat meat product fortified with mushrooms. The moisture content of the product was 70.6%, protein 9.2%, fat 2.9%, and ash 1.2%, carbohydrate 6.0%, and sodium 1.67%, respectively. Total SFA accounted for 30.33%, monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) were 32.11%, while PUFA was 37.34%. The total bacterial count in products stored for 6 months was less than 10³ CFU/g, indicating the product meets hygiene requirements. This type of product is value-added products and offer opportunities to support sustainable pasture management and sustainable production.

Keywords: goat meat products; mushroom fortification; fatty acids; chemical analyses

Introduction

Processed meat and meat products are highly valued for their nutritional composition; however, it's have been criticized due to their

deficiency in dietary fibre and antioxidants and its high content of saturated fat, which has historically been linked to obesity, cardiovascular disease, and high cholesterol. Thus, mushrooms that have a low content of lipid (Jayakumar et al., 2009) and enhancing the oxidative stability of the products by the supportive action of phenolic compounds can be used as a substitute or additive (Manzi et al., 2000, Perez et al., 2021,).

Mushrooms have properties that can prevent cancer, lower blood lipids, and act as an antioxidant (Yadav and Negi 2021). Nevertheless, even with the current interest in functional meat developments, there are limited investigations that focused on the interaction between oyster mushrooms and goat meat because the latter has a distinct fatty acid composition and is leaner than beef or lamb. This research aims to establish the effectiveness of oyster mushrooms as a biological preservative in extending the shelf life of meat products.

Materials and methods

Three-year-old Mongolian native goats (n=3) from Dundgovi province were slaughtered at the slaughterhouse. The goat carcasses were chilled and deboned. Meat samples were vacuum-packed and frozen at -18°C until subsequent analysis. Edible oyster mushrooms were obtained from the “Mongolian mushrooms” plant, where they were grown under controlled conditions at 22–25°C and 80–85% humidity.

Moisture content was measured by the standard GB 5009.3–2016. Fat content analyzed using the Soxhlet extraction method. Protein content was determined via the Kjeldahl method. Ash content was measured by GB 5009.4–2016. Total carbohydrates calculated using formula. Sodium content by flame AS GB 5009.91–2017. Fatty acid profile of products was carried out by the standard GB 5009.168-2016– Determination of Fatty Acids in Foods.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of the product is shown in Table 1. The moisture content was 70.6%, protein 9.2%, fat 2.9%, and ash

1.2%, respectively. The product had 6.0% carbohydrate content and 1.67% sodium.

Table 1. Chemical composition of goat meat product fortified with mushrooms

Moisture, %	70.6	Carbohydrate, %	6.0
Total fat, %	2.9	Sodium, %	1.67
Protein, %	9.2	Energy, kJ/100g	366
Minerals (ash), %	1.2	-	-

Fatty acid analysis revealed linoleic acid (34.2%) as the major fatty acid, followed by oleic acid (30.0%) and palmitic acid (17.2%). The ready-to-eat product showed a balanced ratio of PUFA (37.34%) and MUFA (32.11%), with total saturated fatty acids (SFA) ranging from 30.33%. The higher content of linoleic acid in the product aligns with oyster mushrooms' reputation as a source of heart-healthy fatty acids.

Table 2. The fatty acid profile of the ready-to-eat meat product fortified with mushrooms %

Lipid Numbers	Values	Lipid Numbers	Values
C14:0	1.22	C14:1	0.045
C15:0	0.299	C16:1	1.18
C16:0	17.2	C18:1	30.0
C17:0	0.692	C18:2	34.2
C18:0	10.3	C18:3	3.07
C20:0	0.274	C20:1	0.678
C21:0	0.033	C20:4n6	0.054
C22:0	0.033	C20:5n3	0.017
C24:0	0.0851	C22:1	0.252
Total SFA	30.33	Total MUFA	32.11
		Total PUFA	37.34

Similar results have documented that oyster mushrooms have lower fat content. The main fatty acid present in oyster mushrooms was linoleic acid and another fatty acid common in mushrooms, known as oleic acid and the relatively high concentration of linoleic acid is one of the reasons that mushrooms are considered a nutritionally healthy food (Jayakumar et al., 2009, Yadav D, Negi PS. (2021).

Microbiological stability and shelf life

The fortified meat products showed no detectable bacterial growth even at 6 months, attributed to their low moisture content. Microbiological assessment showed that total bacterial counts remained below 10^3 CFU/g throughout storage at 37°C, during 56 days, and at room temperature, counts stayed below 10^1 CFU/g for 6 months. This confirms that product mushroom fortified maintains microbial stability, supporting shelf-life for up to 6 months under proper storage conditions.

Conclusion

Microbiological evaluation of the product showed that it could be stored up to six months under safe microbial limits and, therefore, as shelf-stable and suitable for consumers due to its nutritional value. Further studies are required to evaluate the nutritional composition of oyster mushrooms on a larger number of samples to ensure the accuracy of the nutritional contents presented.

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New Records of the Genus *Pleurotus* (*Pleurotaceae*, *Basidiomycota*) to the Fungal Flora of Mongolia

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Abstract

This article presents data on the morphology from the species of the species of Chiir's mushroom (genus of *Pleurotus* (Fr.) P. Kumm) collected from western Mongolia. Effective methods of preserving the gene pool of valuable edible and medicinal mushrooms of genera *Pleurotus* are to correctly identify and verify the preserved sample. Therefore, to clarify the taxonomic classification, morphological and genetic studies were conducted and the results were compared. We study, which involved DNA gene analyses in combination with a morphological analysis, showed that Chiir's mushroom is divergent from its related groups at the morphology (spore size) and DNA.

The chiir's mushroom is a separate phylogenetic species within the *P. eryngii* complex and may be a separate species *Pleurotus tuoliensis* or *Pleurotus nebrodensis*. Therefore, further genetic and morphological studies, as well as in-depth analysis of mycelium growth, are needed.

Keywords: *Pleurotus*, chiir's mushroom, new record, fungal flora, Mongolia,

Introduction

The genus *Pleurotus* (Fr.) P. Kumm is placed under the family *Pleurotaceae* Kühner (Agaricales, Basidiomycota). The *Pleurotaceae*

are a family of small to medium-sized mushrooms which have white spores including 6 genera and 94 species (Kirk & al. 2008).

To date, approximately 677 species of higher fungi belonging to 284 genera and 119 families of fungus have been recognized from Mongolia (Kherlenchimeg et al., 2024). There are 6 species of genus *Pleurotus* recorded in Mongolia. Six species of genera *Pleurotus* (*P. calyptratus* (Lindblad ex Fr.) Sacc., *P. citrinopileatus* Singer, *P. cornucopiae* (Paulet) Rolland, *P. dryinus* (Pers.) P. Kumm., *P. ostreatus* (Jacq.) P. Kumm., *P. pulmonarius* (Fr.) Quel.) have previously been reported in Mongolia (Kherlenchimeg et al., 2017; 2024). Species within the genus *Pleurotus* are globally recognized for their superior organoleptic properties and a nutritional profile rich in essential amino acids, dietary fiber, and vital micronutrients. These culinary-medicinal mushrooms exhibit significant therapeutic potential, including the inhibition of colon cancer cell proliferation, immunomodulation, and antimicrobial activity against clinically significant pathogens. Beyond their health benefits, their high commercial value and adaptability for *ex situ* cultivation offer substantial opportunities for sustainable local economic development. This study aimed to characterize the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) region of the 'Chiir's Mushroom' (locally known as Chiiriin moog), a saprotrophic or weakly parasitic fungus found on the rhizomes of *Ferula ferulaeoides* in the Ikh Ongog region of Khovd Province, Mongolia.

Materials and methods

We used 25 sheets of herbarium specimen in Botanic Garden and Research Institute (FUBA), Mongolian Academy of Sciences, to revise species composition in the genus *Pleurotus* in Mongolia. The study used samples of Chiir's mushrooms collected by D. Nyambayar, N. Kherlenchimeg, M. Urgamal, and G. Monkhtulga from the Ikh Ongoi region of Khovd province, Mongolia in 2011 and 2025. Collected from the rhizome of *Ferula ferulaeoides*. The study used samples of the Chiir mushroom collected by D. Nyambayar, N. Kherlenchimeg, M. Urgamal, and G. Monkhtulga. Not only the results of molecular genetic studies,

but also morphological characteristics were considered as additional criteria.

Results and Discussion

The mushroom of the genus *Pleurotus* in the Ikh Ongog region of Khovd Province, Mongolia, called the 'Chiir's Mushroom' (locally known as Chiiriin moog), is a precious edible fungus with high economic value. However, the most essential information on the taxonomic status of Chiiriin moog and its phylogenetic relationships with its sibling species remain uncertain. Therefore, to clarify the taxonomic classification, morphological and genetic studies were conducted and the results were compared. M

Mushrooms from *Pleurotus* genus that grow on the roots of Apiaceae plants belong to the *P.eryngii* species complex. Basidiospores of Chiir's mushroom 14.3–18 (19.7) × 6.4–8.5 μm, cylindrical, smooth. Basidiospores of *Pleurotus nebrodensis* 12.5–15.1 (18) × 5.2–6.1 μm, asymmetrical, cylindrical to phaseoliform, smooth, and of *Pleurotus tuoliensis* (9) 10–14 × (4.2) 5–6 μm, oblong-elliptic to elliptic, colorless and hyaline. It is seen from this that the spores of the Chiir's mushroom are large, so it is necessary to continue studying them further.

Conclusion

We study, which involved DNA gene analyses in combination with a morphological analysis, showed that Chiir's mushroom is divergent from its related groups at the morphology (spore size) and DNA. The chiir's mushroom is a separate phylogenetic species within the *P. eryngii* complex and may be a separate species *Pleurotus tuoliensis* or *Pleurotus nebrodensis*. Therefore, further genetic and morphological studies, as well as in-depth analysis of mycelium growth, are needed.

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Hidden ectomycorrhiza: Organ-specific endophytic fungal communities in *Larix sibirica* seedlings reveal unexpected *Russula* in both above-and belowground tissues

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Abstract

Understanding how endophytic fungal communities are structured across plant organs and environmental gradients is central to clarifying their ecological roles in forest ecosystems (Rodriguez et al., 2009; Hardoim et al., 2015). In the boreal forests of Mongolia, *Larix sibirica* (Siberian larch) represents a dominant ectomycorrhizal tree species; however, the composition and functional characteristics of its endophytic fungal communities remain incompletely understood, particularly with respect to organ-specific patterns and variation among forest types.

In this study, we investigated endophytic fungal assemblages associated with needles, stems, and roots of *L. sibirica* seedlings collected from two contrasting forest types. Endophytic fungal communities were characterized using high-throughput sequencing of the ITS region, and their ecological functions were inferred using the FUNGuild and FungalTraits databases (Pölme et al., 2020). Community composition differed markedly among plant organs, highlighting tissue type as a primary determinant of endophytic fungal

structure, consistent with previous studies (Oono et al., 2015; Eo et al., 2014). In contrast, the influence of forest type was less pronounced and was mainly evident in root-associated communities, suggesting that host-related factors outweigh environmental variation (Qin et al., 2024).

Functional analyses revealed distinct trophic patterns among plant organs. Saprotrophic fungi were more commonly detected in aboveground tissues, whereas symbiotrophic fungi were relatively more abundant in roots, reflecting ecological differentiation (Porrás-Alfaro and Bayman, 2011; Latz et al., 2018). In addition, many taxa were assigned to multiple trophic modes, indicating ecological flexibility and potential functional shifts under changing environmental conditions.

Key words: fungal endophytes; high-throughput sequencing; trophic modes; organ-specific distribution; boreal forest

Conclusion

Our results demonstrate that plant organ is a primary driver of endophytic fungal community structure in *Larix sibirica*, exceeding the influence of forest type. The observed organ-specific and functional differentiation underscores the ecological importance of endophytic fungi in boreal forest ecosystems and highlights their potential roles in ecosystem functioning.

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Evaluation of Physical Mutagenesis Effects on *Flammulina velutipes*

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Abstract

Research has been done on creating mutant variants that yield higher amounts of crop by stimulating mushroom mycelium with physical, chemical stimulants such as ultraviolet radiation, ethyl methanesulfonate, methyl methanesulfonate. There also has been research done on stimulating *Flammulina velutipes* with physical mutagens. There were 820 pairs of base length when using PCR with primers ITS1, and ITS4 which proves that there was no change in the rRNA. PCR(RAPD) was randomly chosen. On primers RAPD, RAPD9: samples affected for 3 hours, 6 hours, 9 hours show main parts, which are 3000, 1500, and 2000 pairs of base lengths in number. On primer RAPD10: samples affected for 3 hours, 6 hours, and 9 hours in different states which was 3000 base lengths different in number. This genetic property proves that there was a mutation. When electrophoresis is done on polyacrylamide gel in ultraviolet radiation for 3 hours, 6 hours, 9 hours, 12 hours, there's an increase in protein synthesis. This shows that there was a mutation on either signal factor, or regulation gene activity.

Keywords: *Flammulina velutipes*, enokitake, fungi, mutants, RAPD PCR

Introduction

F. velutipes is one of the most important edible mushrooms in tropical countries in terms of mushroom production (Chang et al., 1996). The English scientist Ingolda believed that the cold resistance of *Flammulina velutipes* is due to the high protein content in its vegetative body (up to 30%). It also has a rare ability to synthesize biologically active substances. Various anti-tumor preparations have been obtained from its vegetative and fibrous bodies. Japanese scientists have determined that this mushroom contains a large number of substances that enhance human memory and intellectual abilities, such as arginine and lysine. There is experience in producing mutant strains and improving them to obtain high yields by stimulating the mycelium of the mushroom with physical and chemical agents such as gamma rays, ultraviolet rays, ethyl methanesulfonate, and methyl methanesulfonate (E. Bangyeekhun et al., 2020). Therefore, we mutated *Flammulina velutipes* to identify and cultivate macromolecules, which is the basis of this research work.

Materials and methods

The samples were exposed to 38 W of UV light at a wavelength of 250 nm at a distance of 4 cm for 3, 6, 9, and 12 hours. After UV irradiation, the plates were removed from light and placed in the dark at 23°C for 48 hours. The UV dose was set to induce a survival rate of approximately 25% for the mutant strain.

PCR conditions using ITS primers: Taq 2x Dual master mix was used to prepare the master mix (2x PCR buffer pH=8.5, 500 µmol each dNTP, 2.5 µmol MgCl₂, Taq DNA polymerase) and the total reaction volume was 20 µl. The PCR program was set to run for 35 cycles of initial denaturation at 95°C-10 min, subsequent denaturation at 95°C-30 sec, annealing at 60°C-40 sec, extension at 72°C-40 sec, and 72°C-5 min. Using RAPD primers, the PCR program was set to run the first denaturation at 95°C-5 minutes, the next denaturation at 95°C-1 minute, annealing at 36°C-1 minute, extension at 72°C-2 minutes, and 72°C-7 minutes. After 45 cycles, the sample was removed from the

PCR machine and gel electrophoresis was performed on a 1-2% agarose gel.

Results and Discussion

The cultivation technology of *F. velutipes* mushroom has been studied in developed countries such as Japan, Taiwan, China, South Korea, and Malaysia. Researchers Ayushi Kamthan and Mohan Kamthan, (2015) found that the mycelium of *F. velutipes* mushroom grew at a rate of 0.4-0.8 mm per day at a temperature of 18°C-22°C in PDA medium. Our study showed that the mycelium of *F. velutipes* mushroom grew at a rate of 0.5 mm per day at a temperature of 23°C in PDA medium, which is similar to the results of the above scientists. In a study conducted by researchers Eakaphun Bangyeekhun (2020), samples were exposed to ultraviolet light (100µJ/cm²) in HybriLinker HL-2000 UV Crosslinker for 0-60 minutes, resulting in the formation of mutants. When analyzed using RAPD primers, it was found that the two high-yielding strains were genetically different from the parent strain, which showed the same results as our experiment. Therefore, it is concluded that the use of RAPD primers is suitable for examining the differences in the genotypes of mutagenesis-induced fungi and yeasts.

Eakaphun Bangyeekhun (2020) After UV irradiation, the predicted mutant strains were obtained and seven fast-growing strains were selected for analysis. Mushroom cultivation experiments showed that the biological efficiency of the four strains was approximately 30% higher than that of the parent strain. The growth rate of the mycelial colonies was evaluated under different conditions of media, temperature, and pH. The results showed that the growth rate of the mutant strains was higher than that of the parent strain, which is similar to the growth rate of 12-28% in our study.

In a study conducted by Mayumi Nakamura, Aya Iketani, and Yuzo Shioi (2011), the protease enzyme activity of *F. velutipes* mushroom was 0.52 n/ml, while in our study, the activity of the control sample was 0.46 n/ml, while the enzyme activity of the 9-hour sample treated with physical mutagen showed the highest value of 0.61 n/ml. This shows that the sample with a mutation of ±0.15 n/ml is more.

Conclusion

In this study, we identified macromolecules by mutating the fungus *Flammulina velutipes*. The following conclusions are summarized from the results of the study. PCR using ITS1 and ITS4 primers resulted in the amplification of a product with a length of 820 base pairs, confirming that there was no mutagenic change in the 5.8S region located between 18S rRNA and 28S rRNA in the rRNA. PCR using a randomly selected leader (RAPD) amplified products with a length of 3000, 1500 and 2000 base pairs in samples treated with RAPD8 and RAPD9 primers at 3 hours, 6 hours and 9 hours, while a product with a length of 3000 base pairs was amplified in samples treated with RAPD10 primer at 3 hours, 6 hours and 9 hours, which is a difference. From this, the genotypic characteristics confirm that the mutation occurred. When conducting polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis, the protein synthesis of the samples exposed to ultraviolet light for 3 hours, 6 hours, 9 hours, and 12 hours increased. In conclusion, the study suggests that the signal factor and regulatory gene activity involved in gene synthesis may have been mutated or that the enhancer of gene synthesis may have become a stimulator. The activity of the protease enzyme increased by 17-31% compared to the control.

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Evaluation of the mycelial growth of *Hericium erinaceus* on various substrate formulations

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the optimal substrate formulations for the vegetative growth of *H. erinaceus* by evaluating various lignocellulosic materials and organic supplements. In the initial phase, five pure substrates (wheat straw, oat straw, birch, elm, and pine sawdust) were screened. Based on the radial growth performance, oat straw was selected as the basal medium. Subsequently, six enriched variants were developed by supplementing oat straw with wheat bran (5%, 10%, 20%) and horse manure (5%, 10%, 20%). Mycelial radial growth was monitored daily over an 11-day incubation period at 25°C in total darkness. Pure substrate screening revealed that birch sawdust (3.92±0.09 cm) and oat straw (3.90±0.13 cm) facilitated the highest growth rates, while pine sawdust was least effective. In the second phase, one-way ANOVA confirmed that supplementation significantly enhanced growth ($F(6, 28) = 6.22, P < 0.001$). The variant supplemented with 20% wheat bran demonstrated superior performance, reaching full colonization (4.00±0.01 cm) by day 11, followed closely by 20% horse manure (3.98±0.05 cm). In contrast, the control group (100% oat straw) reached only 3.19±0.52 cm. The findings suggest that supplementing oat straw with 20% nitrogen-rich organic additives optimizes the Carbon-to-Nitrogen (C/N) ratio and provides essential micronutrients for *H. erinaceus*.

Keywords: mushroom, substrate optimization, mycelial, supplementation

Introduction

Hericium erinaceus (Lion's mane) is globally distributed and predominantly occurs in high-altitude and temperate regions. It is widely found across North and South America, Europe, Australia, China, Japan, and other Asian countries (Ginns, 1985). *Hericium erinaceus*, most commonly known as lion's mane, is an edible fungus, with a long history of use in Traditional Chinese Medicine. The mushroom is abundant in bioactive compounds including β -glucan polysaccharides; hericenones and erinacine terpenoids; isoindolinones; sterols; and myconutrients, which potentially have neuroprotective and neuroregenerative properties. Because of its anti-inflammatory properties and promotion of nerve growth factor gene expression and neurite (axon or dendrite) outgrowth, *H. erinaceus* mycelium shows great promise for the treatment of Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases (Kevin Spelman, 2017). In 1959, China successfully isolated pure strains of *Hericium erinaceus* (Bull.) Pers. and achieved artificial domestication (Ling ZL, 2025). Developing substrate variants for the cultivation of *Hericium erinaceus* is of significant scientific, economic, and medicinal importance. The scientifically grounded development of cultivation substrates enables year-round continuous production independent of natural environmental conditions, while ensuring consistent product quality and stable concentrations of bioactive compounds. The objective of this study is to develop optimal substrate variants for the cultivation of *Hericium erinaceus*.

Materials and methods

A pure culture of *Hericium erinaceus*, sourced from the USA, was utilized in this study. In the initial phase to identify suitable substrates, wheat straw, oat straw, birch sawdust, elm sawdust, and pine sawdust were evaluated individually (100% concentration). Each raw material was finely chopped and moistened with distilled water to achieve a 70% moisture content. The substrates were then packed into Petri dishes and sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 20 minutes.

The sterilized substrates were inoculated with mycelial plugs and incubated at 25°C in total darkness. Mycelial radial growth was measured daily until the Petri dishes were fully colonized. Based on the results of the initial screening, the substrate that exhibited the most significant effect on mycelial growth was selected as the basal medium. This base material was then supplemented with wheat bran (5%, 10%, 20%) and horse manure (5%, 10%, 20%) to create six additional variants. The preparation, sterilization, and inoculation protocols for these mixed substrates followed the aforementioned methodology.

Results and Discussion

Mycelial Growth Performance of *H. erinaceus* on Pure Substrates

The mycelial radial growth of *H. erinaceus* was monitored over a 12-day incubation period (Figure 1). Birch sawdust and oat straw substrates facilitated the highest growth rates, reaching final radii of 3.92 ± 0.09 cm and 3.90 ± 0.13 cm, respectively. In contrast, pine sawdust exhibited significantly lower performance (1.63 ± 0.29 cm), likely due to its resinous composition. Mycelial radial growth of *H. erinaceus* on pure substrate variants over 12 days. Each data point represents the Mean \pm SD (n=5). Significant differences between substrates were confirmed by one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.001$).

Figure 1. Mycelial radial growth *H. erinaceus* on pure substrate variants over 12 days

Figure 2. Mycelial growth of *H. erinaceus* on mixed

Mycelial Growth on Supplemented Oat Straw Substrates

The mycelial radial growth of *H. erinaceus* on oat straw supplemented with wheat bran and horse manure is presented in Figure 2. Statistical analysis using one-way ANOVA confirmed that the substrate composition had a highly significant effect on the mycelial growth rate by day 11 ($P < 0.001$).

Overall, all supplemented variants exhibited faster colonization compared to the non-supplemented oat straw (control). The growth promotion followed a clear dose-response pattern, where increasing the concentration of supplements led to more vigorous mycelial expansion.

Among the tested formulations, oat straw supplemented with 20% wheat bran demonstrated the superior growth performance. This variant reached a maximum radius of 4.00 ± 0.01 cm by day 11, achieving full colonization of the Petri dish. This was followed closely by the 20% horse manure supplement, which reached a radius of 3.98 ± 0.05 cm. In contrast, the control group (100% oat straw) showed significantly slower development, reaching only 3.19 ± 0.52 cm by the end of the incubation period. These findings suggest that 20% wheat bran is the most effective additive for optimizing the vegetative growth of *H. erinaceus* on an oat straw-based medium.

Conclusion

The results indicate that supplementing oat straw with nitrogen-rich organic additives significantly accelerates the vegetative growth of *H. erinaceus*. The superior performance of 20% wheat bran (3.99 ± 0.01 cm) and 20% horse manure (3.98 ± 0.05 cm) variants, supported by a significant F-value (6.22, $P < 0.001$), suggests that pure oat straw is nutrient-deficient for rapid colonization. This growth promotion is primarily due to the optimization of the Carbon-to-Nitrogen (C/N) ratio. While oat straw provides a stable carbon source, wheat bran adds essential organic nitrogen, vitamins B, and minerals that act as enzymatic co-factors. Similarly, horse manure provides pre-digested lignocellulosic fibers and processed nitrogen, facilitating easier absorption by the mycelium.

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Physical characteristics of sausage enriched with mushroom powder

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Abstract

This study investigated the physical characteristics of pork sausages fortified with oyster mushroom powder. The sausages were formulated with oyster mushroom powder at concentrations of 0 %, 0.5 %, 1.0 %, and 3.0 % (designated as CTL, M1, M2, and M3, respectively). Water-holding capacity remained stable across all treatments (85.4-88.0 % at day 0), converging to 90.4-90.8 % by day 49. Texture profile analysis demonstrated that M1 (0.5 %) maintained optimal textural properties with the highest cohesiveness (0.59 ± 0.01) and chewiness (51.2 ± 1.75 g) values. That oyster mushroom powder at concentrations up to 1.0 % can serve as a multifunctional ingredient for texture enhancement in emulsified meat products.

Keywords: *Pleurotus ostreatus*, color parameters, textural properties, water-holding capacity

Introduction

Edible mushrooms have emerged as promising functional ingredients for meat product development due to their unique nutritional composition and bioactive compound profiles (Das *et al.*, 2021; Torres-Martínez *et al.*, 2022). Guevara *et al.* (2020) reported that frankfurter sausages formulated with 2.5% and 5% *P. ostreatus* flour exhibited nutritional profiles. Comprehensive evaluations comparing

the physical characteristics of meat products enriched with mushroom powders are limited. Furthermore, extended storage studies (beyond 28 days) examining the effects of mushroom powder on the physicochemical parameters, textural properties are necessary to establish optimal incorporation levels for commercial application. This research aims to establish evidence-based recommendations for oyster mushroom powder incorporation levels that optimize technological functionality in emulsified meat products, thereby contributing to the development of healthier processed meat formulations.

Materials and methods

Color parameters were measured using a CR-10 colorimeter (Minolta, Tokyo, Japan). Water-holding was measured using centrifuge method of Wierbicki and Deatherage (1958). Texture profile values evaluated using a texture analyzer (Brookfield CT3, Ametek, USA).

Results

Figure 1. Changes in water-holding capacity (WHC) of pork sausage during refrigerated storage. (CTL = Control, M1, M2, M3 = different treatment levels. Different letters (A-C) at the same storage day indicate significant differences among treatments ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Changes in texture properties and physical characteristics of pork sausage with oyster mushroom powder during refrigerated storage. Hardness, Adhesiveness, Resilience, Chewiness, CTL = Control, M1 = 0.5 % oyster mushroom powder, M2 = 1.0 % oyster mushroom powder, M3 = 3.0 % oyster mushroom powder.

Conclusion

The extended 49-day refrigerated storage evaluation of oyster mushroom-fortified pork sausages revealed concentration-dependent effects on quality parameters, with the 1.0% incorporation level (M2) emerging as the optimal formulation. Water-holding capacity converged across all treatments by day 7 and progressively improved to 90.4-90.8 % by day 49, indicating that oyster mushroom polysaccharides establish effective water-binding mechanisms that compensate for the partial replacement of meat proteins.

Texture profile analysis revealed that the M1 treatment (0.5 %)

maintained optimal textural characteristics with the highest cohesiveness (0.59 ± 0.01) and chewiness (51.2 ± 1.75 g) values, while M2 demonstrated balanced textural properties suitable for diverse consumer preferences.

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